

INVESTIGATING THE LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES AND LANGUAGE COMPETENCE AMONG ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS: A CONVERGENT PARALLEL STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 9

Pages: 947-993

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2617

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14061369

Manuscript Accepted: 10-15-2024

Investigating the Language Learning Strategies and Language Competence among English Major Students: A Convergent Parallel Study

Cyril Glen B. Grapa, * Mary Ann Ronith P. Libago
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to investigate the language learning strategies and their contribution to the language competence of English major students in the teacher education program at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. The researcher utilized a mixed-method design using the convergent parallel approach. Participants were English major students across all year levels at the college institution, with 204 students randomly selected for the quantitative phase and approximately 10 students purposively selected for the qualitative phase: 5 for in-depth interviews and 5 for focused group discussions. The results indicated that both the level of language learning strategies and language competence were high; the findings were rejected, which reveals that there is significant relationship between them. Further, the findings from both the quantitative and qualitative phases largely converged however, there was one divergent indicator. The study confirmed that language learning strategies significantly impact the enhancement of language competencies among English major students, facilitating effective and efficient language use in realistic contexts. It is recommended that language learners must also prioritize memory strategies despite from the indicators' lowest mean based from the results, such as mnemonic devices and spaced repetition techniques, to enhance vocabulary and grammar retention. Additionally, to improve speaking competency, students should engage in practical applications of the language within their specific contexts, allowing them to practice and develop fluency, essential for effective communication in professional, social, and academic environments.

Keywords: *language learning strategies, language competence, mix methods, English major students, Philippines*

Introduction

In general, language competence displays the level of student's ability to speak, write, read, listen and comprehend regardless of how the specific target language will be used in various contexts (Armea et al., 2022). It is essential for students as it deals many opportunities such in effective communication, build connection among other cultures and especially, it secures growth and development for academic attainment on student's performance. According to Ghambir (2020), EFL students find this a difficulty when conveying a particular viewpoint in some point of contexts, they are hindered to choose and feel a lack of adequate terminology to build their idea. Most of EFL students think first about their native language before translating it to English. In these circumstances, students who believed to have lower levels of language competence, more behavioral issues, and less academic achievement face these hurdles. Hence, there is a result of mismatch between developmental capability and academic expectation.

In global setting according to Ghambir (2020), Nepalese students have a difficult time when speaking, reading and comprehending English even after earning their degrees. Along with the position of English in Nepal, there are so many problems in the context of their language competence in English. In Thailand, students also faced difficulties in terms of language competence specifically in English language. Most of the students have lack of language skills as well knowledge and ability to use English in various social and academic contexts. Therefore, students may find it difficult to use the language in socializing and several factors that affects the student's potential when using the language. Hence, students have lack of language experience, such as grammatical capabilities, lack of vocabulary, knowledge and motivation to learn the language (Sasum & Weeks, 2018).

In the Philippine setting according to Pachina (2020), the country uses the English language as an international language for communication. However, not most people from other countries know that students from the Philippines are also facing difficulties in their language competence especially, when learning to speak English and even write English at all. Further, this was supported according to Evangelista et al. (2019) that students faced difficulties in expressing for Freshmen English majors from College of Teacher Education at Bestlink College. Students have faced challenges in the first stage of tertiary education, particularly in areas like grammar, vocabulary, and macro skills, while encountering fewer difficulties in linguistics. Additionally, students experience obstacles due to the dominant use of their mother tongue for communication, rather than English.

Based from the previous citations presented above, it is highly observed that the language competence especially in English language throughout the world that there are difficulties within the students in each specific context. It is observable in global and even in the national setting. In this context the researcher wanted to conducted this study to investigate the ongoing issue and problem in relation to language competence. In addition to this, findings and results of this study may raise awareness among concerned authorities like the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and Department of Education (DePED) especially on revisiting their curriculum and instruction in order to improve and foster the language competence of the students in English language. Also, teachers may use the findings of the study as their avenue in making new techniques and strategies in the classroom that will allow students to hasten and develop their language competence when speaking, listening, writing, reading and comprehension. The findings of the study are also

great help to the large mass or body in the society with the potential to positively influence educational practices, innovate scaffolding services which accommodates the various needs of each learner, and the overall language competence of the students in English language, thereby contributing to a more effective and inclusive society.

Thus, the researcher has observed that there are lot of studies have been conducted that is focusing on language competence of students regarded in English language. However, most of these studies have been conducted in global and national setting and only few studies have been conducted in the local setting. To cite some, the study of Lozano et al. (2020) which focused on language competence and academic performance of the students by which, it is descriptive by its nature only. Also, the study of (Aguelo, 2017) which focused on enhancing the student's language competence through collaborative learning. Moreover, these studies are different from the present study as the study focuses on language learning strategies of the English major students in accordance to their language competence by a convergent parallel study highlighting on its effect in their competence through speaking, listening, writing, reading and comprehension of the English language. Hence, the present study filled the gap that previous studies failed to examine and explore making new results and findings essential and significant in the field of teaching.

Research Questions

This study investigated language learning strategies and language competence among English major students using a convergent parallel research approach, gathering both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently. This design leverages the strengths of each method to offset their limitations, providing a comprehensive understanding to the problem using combined analysis.

1. What is the level of language learning strategies and language competence among English major students?
2. Is there a significant relationship between language learning strategies and language competence in English major students?
3. What are the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of English major students with regards to their language learning strategies and language competence?
4. What insights do English major students with regards to the effectiveness of language learning strategies in enhancing their language competence?
5. To what extent do the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a mixed methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative techniques as outlined by Battista & Torre (2023). A mixed methods research design involves collecting and analyzing both types of data, combining the results, and aligning the process with relevant theoretical frameworks to effectively achieve the objectives of the study.

This study utilized a mixed methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative research techniques. The quantitative phase employed a tailored survey questionnaire to assess the language learning strategies and language competence of English major students at a local college. In the qualitative phase, the researcher explored participants' perspectives on the key results from the quantitative phase through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

The research design selected for this study was a convergent parallel mixed/triangulation design. In this method, both quantitative and qualitative data were gathered simultaneously, with equal emphasis placed on each. The survey data was collected initially, followed by focus group discussions or individual interviews. The two data sets were analyzed separately before being merged and interpreted together. This design is appropriate for the study, as it aims to examine the alignment, differences, inconsistencies, or relationships between the two data sources, as explained by Hanson et al. (2005).

In this study, the chosen design ensured a thorough exploration of language learning strategies and language competence among English major students at a local college. By collecting quantitative and qualitative data independently, the research provided a multifaceted perspective, and when the findings were combined during interpretation, they offered a comprehensive understanding of the students' language learning strategies in connection with their language competence. This approach enabled a robust analysis of the research problem and its more intricate aspects.

Additionally, this study employed a descriptive correlational design aimed at providing a snapshot of situations and determining the relationships between various variables (McBurney & White, 2009). It offers insights into the strength and direction of these relationships, aiding in the identification of patterns and trends. Since this design is non-experimental, it observes and measures variables as they naturally occur. While it can reveal associations, it does not establish causal links.

In this study, the descriptive correlational research design was used to examine the relationship between two variables: language learning strategies and language competence. The researcher collected data on students' use of different strategies and their proficiency levels. This design helps uncover patterns and correlations between specific strategies and higher language competence. By analyzing these associations, valuable insights can be gained into which strategies may be more effective for language learning. However, it is important to note that this design identifies correlations, not causality.

Moreover, this study included a phenomenological investigation to strengthen the qualitative component. This approach helped reveal and understand the complexities of the participants' experiences in their specific context. Phenomenology focuses on identifying common experiences within a particular group, often through interviews with individuals who have firsthand knowledge of a specific event, situation, or experience. Other data sources, such as documents and observations, may also be utilized (Creswell, 2013).

In this study, this approach was well-suited for uncovering and understanding the intricate details of participants' experiences. Phenomenology concentrated on identifying common elements of lived experiences within a specific group. It involved conducting interviews with individuals who had firsthand knowledge of the events, situations, or experiences under investigation, offering valuable insights into the underlying factors of language learning strategies that influence the language competence of English major students.

Figure 1 below illustrates the convergent parallel mixed methods design utilized in this research. It shows how the quantitative data were collected and analyzed separately from the qualitative data. However, the researcher later merged both datasets to closely examine the convergence and divergence between the findings, providing a more comprehensive analysis.

Figure 1. Convergent Parallel Mixed Method Design

Participants

In this section, the distribution and profile in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed. Additionally, the exclusion criterion is based upon the statuses of English major students and they must not be an irregular student of the said program on the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study were English major student from all year levels in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology during the second semester of S.Y. 2023-2024. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is about language learning strategies and language competence among English major students in a local college. The inclusion criteria guaranteed representation from enrolled students in Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English Program who maintained regular student status, were enrolled in the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024, and were enrolled in their respective courses, which was open to participants of any gender who demonstrated a willingness to participate. Conversely, the irregular students of the said program on the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024 was the exclusion criterion due from their hectic schedule inside the campus. Specifically, one-hundred four (104) first-year students, sixty-four (64) second-year students, thirty-two (32) third-year students and fourteen (14) fourth-year students were selected across all year levels of English major students, totaling two-hundred fourteen (214) participants for the first semester of the academic year 2023-2024. Since, the study purports to involves students who are in the English major program in a local college, it would be fitting and valid to include English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Further, the respondents were determined through sampling, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method involves dividing population into smaller groups, or “strata”, and randomly selecting a sample from each stratum. The per-stratum samples were combined to create an overall stratified random sample. An alternative to simple random sampling, stratified random sampling ensures that each stratum is represented in the sample and can provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen et al., 2020)

Table 1.1. Distribution of Respondents

Year Level	Population	Sample	Percentage
First Year	223	104	22.85%
Second Year	136	64	13.94%
Third Year	69	32	7.07%
Fourth Year	29	14	2.97%
Total	457	214	46.83%

This sampling method was particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents, which were the English major students that was randomly selected based on strata, which in this case all the year levels of the English major education program in Kapalong

College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. This also ensures that all of the respondents in the population have equal chances of being selected. The researcher wrote a formal request letter to the College Registrar and gained access to the population of English major education students from all year levels. The researcher gathered the data from the population of English major education students to compute the sample. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to his statistician for computation of the study sample. The study was conducted among the students enrolled in English teacher education program from all year levels. Participants were covered each of their assigned codes to protect identities and confidentiality.

Qualitative Phase

In contrast, participant selection in qualitative research was intentional. During this phase, a non-probability sampling method, specifically purposive sampling, was employed. Participants were chosen based on their ability to provide valuable insights into the research questions and to deepen understanding of the phenomenon being examined (Kuper et al., 2008). The inclusion criteria guaranteed representation from enrolled students in Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English who maintained regular student status, were enrolled in the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024, and were enrolled in each course, which was open to participants of any gender who demonstrated a willingness to participate. Conversely, the irregular students of the said program on the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024 was the exclusion criterion due from their hectic schedule inside the campus. Only 10 participants of English major students were joined in the qualitative phase: five (5) for in-depth interview and another five (5) for focus group discussion. All of them were English major teacher education student at KCAST and he or she is a 1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year or 4th year student. It should be noted that participants in qualitative phase must not have participated in the data collection of quantitative phases.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Female	First Year
IDI-02	Female	First Year
IDI-03	Female	Second Year
IDI-04	Male	Third Year
IDI-05	Female	Fourth Year
FGD-01	Female	First Year
FGD-02	Female	Second Year
FGD-03	Male	Third Year
FGD-04	Male	Third Year
FGD-05	Female	Fourth Year

Instrument

In this section, the research tools in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study were discussed.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, the researcher utilized an adopted questionnaires from a published and conducted studies of language learning strategies from Fritoty (2020) and language competence from Eslit (2023). Then, these questionnaires were contextualized in the current study according to its focus and context.

After the researcher contextualized the research questionnaire, especially in the construct of each item under each variable, this was further validated and evaluated by an external validators who are all experts in the field of research. Later on, the suggestions and recommendations of the evaluators were followed thoroughly to make the research tool more reliable. Also, the researcher ensured that the questions stipulated in the questionnaire used basic English in order for the respondents to answer each question and comprehend the purpose of the research.

Further, these questionnaires had a Five-point Likert Scale, participants were only required to rate and tick one box among five (always) to one (rarest) in each question. Moreover, Likert Scale was good for measuring constructs, attitudes and stimuli which are not readily perceivable by human senses. Despite the questionnaire being adapted, it was subjected to expert validation. To interpret the perception of organizational commitment, the range of means, description, and interpretation were presented below.

Language Learning Strategies. The questionnaire for this variable was adapted from Fitoty's (2020) study. A reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, resulting in a reliability score of .94, indicating that the questionnaire is reliable. This tool is designed to assess various language learning strategies and consists of 30 items distributed unevenly across six indicators: memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective, and social strategies. Additionally, the tool was validated by research panels, ensuring its suitability for the participants.

Language Competence. The questionnaire for this variable was adapted from Eslit (2023) and includes five indicators: reading, writing, speaking, listening, and comprehension. A reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, yielding a reliability score of .92, indicating that the questionnaire is reliable. The tool consists of 25 items distributed unevenly across the five indicators.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, it used an interview guide which contained the grand core questions and probing and supporting questions which was used both in the in-depth interview and focus group discussions. It was also validated by external validators to check the construct of the questions whether it measures what it intends to measure, or, whether it will get the data needed in the study. In addition, in this phase, the researcher used this validated interview guide to validate the results found in the quantitative phase of the study. Lastly, the interview guide consists of two parts. First for the letter of permission for the participants and the second one is for the interview proper.

Procedure

Several steps were involved in the data collection process. The procedures followed during the study were as follows:

Quantitative Phase

During the quantitative phase, adapted questionnaires were utilized to assess language learning strategies and language competence among English major students. These questionnaires were administered to a group of English major students within a classroom setting. Additionally, the researcher sent a letter of request to the school administrator to obtain approval for conducting the study with their students. The collected data were then tallied, computed, and analyzed to be compared with the qualitative data. Both the qualitative and quantitative phases of the study were conducted simultaneously.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, one-on-one interviews were conducted with selected participants to explore their lived experiences concerning language learning strategies and language competence. An interview guide was employed for both in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. To ensure the authenticity of participant selection, the researcher personally invited informants and informed them about the tasks involved, including scheduling for everyone's convenience (Creswell, 2013). The focus group discussions were designed to delve into individual opinions, experiences, concerns, and aspirations related to the specific issues being studied.

According to Traynor (2015), this method generally involves bringing together a group of individuals with a common characteristic, facilitated by a researcher, to engage in group interactions, share perspectives on a specific topic, discuss personal experiences, and provide suggestions. The focus group research methodology underscores the importance of interaction. The discussions were conducted in various formats, including one-on-one sessions, and were recorded with audio equipment, along with additional notes. Furthermore, in-depth interviews were held to explore English major students' views on their language learning strategies. Ten students were purposively selected for these interviews, which were conducted face-to-face by the researcher and lasted between 20 and 30 minutes.

Data Analysis

This section covers the following aspects: data analysis, sequence, emphasis, and mixing procedures; the procedural framework; anticipated methodological issues; the trustworthiness of the study; the validity of the instruments; and the ethical considerations involved in collecting quantitative and qualitative data from participants, informants, and respondents.

Quantitative Phase

The quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson-r. Here are the discussions to each of the statistical tool: (1) Mean was used to determine the level language learning strategies and language competence of English major students, to answer research questions or problem number 2; (2) Pearson-r was used to determine the significant relationship between language learning strategies and language competence of English major students; (3) Standard Deviation was used to measure how spread out the responses of the respondents are; (4) The collected survey data, which served as the foundation for detailed analysis, were first tallied and processed upon retrieval of the questionnaires. The data were then analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to perform both descriptive and inferential statistical procedures. These statistical treatments were applied to ascertain the status of English major students.

Qualitative Phase

During the qualitative phase, the data gathered from interviews were analyzed, leading to conclusions that confirmed and supported the results from the quantitative phase. As described, data analysis in research involves summarizing the extensive data collected and presenting the findings in a manner that highlights the key aspects of the study (Harding, 2013).

In the study, data analysis occurred after transcribing the results from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with participants. The researcher employed coding and thematic analysis to examine the collected data. For presentation, the data were organized into categories based on similar responses from different participants, a process known as thematic analysis.

For the qualitative data analysis, the researcher utilized coding and thematic analysis. According to Braun & Clarke (2013), thematic analysis is a versatile approach that qualitative researchers used to identify themes from interview data. This method involves examining patterns and themes that arise from participants' statements during one-on-one and focus group interviews. The themes were developed

to analyze the lived experiences of English major students regarding their language learning strategies and language competence. The data were meticulously analyzed to extract relevant themes that illuminate the research objectives and offer insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

To become acquainted with the data, the researcher listened to and transcribed the recorded interviews of the participants, repeatedly reviewing the transcripts to identify similar responses. Once familiar with the data, coding commenced, during which the researcher applied codes to categorize and generate themes and ideas. Similar passages of text were labeled with codes, facilitating their retrieval for further comparison and analysis at later stages.

After clustering the codes, the researcher labeled the clusters based on the meaning or relationships shared among the codes. This step involved naming the codes by using the labels created for each theme and providing a descriptive name that captures the relationship or meaning conveyed by that specific theme.

Finally, to enhance the reliability of the data, the researcher consulted with a data analyst who was an expert in the field and sought further verification from their research adviser. The findings and interpretations of the data were then presented in tabular forms to provide clearer understanding and detailed elaboration.

Ethical Considerations

These principles guided the study's conduct in both qualitative and quantitative phases, ensuring a responsible and respectful approach that prioritized the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005). Measures were taken to address these ethical considerations throughout the mixed-method study. The research adhered to the elements of ethics outlined in the International Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research Involving Humans (2016), including social value, informed consent, consideration of participant vulnerability, justice, transparency, researcher qualifications, adequacy of facilities, community involvement, risk and benefit assessment, and privacy and confidentiality of information. Additionally, the Research Ethics Committee reviewed and validated the manuscript multiple times before the study was conducted to ensure adherence to ethical principles.

Social Value. The researcher of the study aimed to address the social problems pertaining to the language learning strategies helping to enhance the language competence of English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. With this study, it aimed to address the challenges encountered by the English major students in implementing effective strategies in language learning that fits to their personal preference helping to enhance their overall language competence in diverse aspects. This also served as the basis for the institution for adhering developments needed for the program, concerning the needs of English major students solely to the purpose of enhancing their language competence. Also, this could be an advantage for the English major students as they could get insights that are related to the strategies effective to enhance and develop their current language competence to their full potential. Further, the study serves as an embodiment of knowledge which includes presentations and publication in scientific forums or journals to share the study's findings contributed to the broader body of knowledge within their field of study.

Additionally, the researcher thoroughly explained the overall procedure to ensure full participation of English major students across all year levels, clarifying the study's main purpose and the data collection process. The results were shared with the participants and disseminated to other relevant audiences who could benefit from the study. The researcher maintained a commitment to social value by rigorously applying the convergent parallel mixed-method design used in the study.

Informed Consent. To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, the researcher of the study provided the participants with letters of permission and consent in both qualitative and quantitative that outlined the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and made informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who did not decide to participate are allowed to leave without any explanations and assured that their data remained confidential. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted in a responsible and respectful manner.

Vulnerability of the Research Participants. The research of the study was fully taken into consideration the vulnerability of the participants. Further, the conduction of both qualitative and quantitative data was fully addressed with consents stipulated with their signature that signifies that they agreed to participate in the data gathering hence, English major students were less vulnerable from the study. Additionally, the interview as well as the dissemination of survey questionnaires were given specific schedules based upon the convenience of the participants. Lastly, participants were given tokens for their efforts in the participation to succeed the study.

The Risks, Benefits and Safety. As an ethical principle, the researcher emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected. Additionally, the data gathered during this research study was exclusively utilized for the specified research objectives. The study's outcomes may also be disseminated through various means, including presentations within the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, and presentations at conferences, whether on a local, national, or international scale. The researcher's intent in sharing the study's findings contributed to the broader body of knowledge within their field of study.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. Towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques were used. Conversely, all personal identities of the participants were hidden and not shown including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data and others should be eliminated right after the data is analyzed. Further, to protect the participant's identity and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher used discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, the researcher was able to protect the participant's identity and ensure that their privacy was respected.

Justice. In this study, the researcher ensured the rights of the participants who identified themselves as English major students. Given that the study aimed to explore the language learning strategies and language competence, no rights of minor students will be violated. In recognition of their contribution, they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Additionally, English major students are not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they so choose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, and duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Also, justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them.

Transparency. The study adhered to principles of transparency by fully informing participants that the research focused on the experiences and insights of English major students regarding their language learning strategies and language competence across all year levels at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Additionally, the researcher had no personal connection to the identified participants, as purposive sampling was used to select English major students across all year levels without subjectivity or bias related to their statuses. Interview notes and transcriptions were presented to participants for their confirmation and approval, and the results were also shared with them by the researcher.

Qualifications of the Researcher. The researcher of the study was credible to undertake the study of mixed design about investigating the language learning strategies and language competence among English major students, as the researcher is a third-year student of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English and were enrolled from the course Language Research 2 in fulfillment for the requirement. Furthermore, the study had undergone multiple validations which was started from the researchers' adviser up to the panelists making sure that it is appropriate and has the standard from the principles of thesis writing. Additionally, the interpretation of the statistical data was credible due to the researcher's background in Statistics. The selection of the municipality and the college institution for the study was justified by the researcher's residency in the nearby municipality, which provided practical relevance and accessibility for the research.

Adequacy of Facilities. The adequacy of facilities addressed by the researcher since, the study only utilized resources that are already available such as the bond papers for the questionnaires, cellphone for the audio and tracking of the responses, as well as the laptop and printer which was the primary facility to succeed the study. Further, the source of funds was supported by the parents of the researcher, including the resources to be used in disseminating survey questionnaires for the quantitative part, tokens and snacks for the interviewees in the qualitative part, also the research fee which attained a significant amount to undergo the outline defense and final-defense. Thus, after gathering the significant data, the researcher directly consulted to the data analyst for guiding corrections and improvements for the themes. Further, the researcher consulted also to the certified statistician for the correct interpretation of the data. Hence, these things were undergone to avoid any delay to come up with immediate result and complete the required publication from the institution.

Community Involvement. The study involved a community of English major students across all year levels in the institution by which, it is the solely focused of the study and should be presented. These students had come across with their experiences to diverse strategies particular in language learning and developing their language competence to their full potential. Further, the results may gather insights for the future endeavors making it as their instrument in grasping knowledge and solving problems in the field from this study. Lastly, the beneficiaries of the study were part of the community where in the college institution, where also the study was conducted.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the results from both the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study. The first phase focuses on the quantitative aspect, displaying the status of English major students' language learning strategies and the variables that significantly predict their language competence. The second phase presents qualitative data in a matrix format, which outlines participants' responses about their lived experiences related to their language learning strategies and English language competence. The matrix includes the issues explored, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes, and supporting theoretical perspectives. Additionally, another matrix integrates the key quantitative and qualitative findings.

Status of Language Learning Strategies

Presented in the table 2 is the status of Language Learning Strategies (LLS) of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English students across all year levels who were classified as students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Also, the

table presented the items that has the highest and the lowest mean rating in each indicator. Moreover, items on each indicator were given a description level from very high to low. On the other hand, each description was given an interpretation which depend upon the level on how English major students certainly manifested language learning strategies across all year levels. To support understanding, the study provided an overall illustration from a comprehensive examination based from data being collected from the participants.

Shown in the table 2 is the overall mean rating of language learning strategies which obtained an overall mean rating of 4.6 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Additionally, the variable of the study which is the language learning strategies which have five indicators such: memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective and social.

Table 2. *Status of Language Learning Strategies*

Variables and Indicators	Mean	Description
A. Memory		
1. Thinking in the relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in English	4.15	High
2. Using new English words in a sentence, so I can remember them	3.98	High
3. Connecting the sound of a new word and an image or picture of the word to help remember the word	3.86	High
4. Remembering a new English word by making a mental picture of a situation in which the word might be used	3.92	High
5. Reviewing English lessons daily	3.76	High
Category Mean	3.93	High
B. Cognitive		
1. Using English when writing essays and academic reports to	4.40	Very High
2. Using English language when presenting a Report or augmenting ideas	4.07	High
3. Making summaries in English with the Information that I hear or read	4.00	High
4. Watching TV shows or movies that are spoken in English	4.13	High
5. Looking for words in my own language that are similar to new words in English	4.86	High
Category Mean	4.09	High
C. Compensation		
1. Making guesses to understand unfamiliar English words	3.94	High
2. Using gestures when I cannot think of a word during a conversation in English	4.09	High
3. Thinking of similar words when I encounter	4.07	High
4. Attempting to anticipate the person's upcoming words in English when expressing	3.74	High
5. Using a word or phrase that means the same thing when I cannot think of an English word	3.99	High
Category Mean	3.97	High

Memory. In the first indicator, it obtained an overall mean rating of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Shown in the result that item no. 1 - thinking in the relationships between what I already know and new things I learned in English obtained the highest mean rating of 4.15 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is always manifested by the English major students across all year levels. While, item no. 5 - reviewing English lessons daily obtained the lowest mean 3.76 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Cognitive. Moreover, the second indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means, that it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Shown in the result that item no. 1 - using English when writing essays and academic reports obtained the highest mean rating of 4.40 with a descriptive equivalent as very high. This

means that, it is always manifested by the English major students across all year levels. While, item no. 5 - looking for words in my own language that are similar to new words in English obtained the lowest mean of 3.84 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Compensation. Further, the third indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 3.97 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Shown in the result that item no. 2 - using gestures when I cannot think of a word during a conversation in English obtained the highest mean rating of 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. While, item no. 2 - attempting to anticipate the person's upcoming words in English when expressing obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.74 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the students across all year levels.

Metacognitive. Furthermore, the fourth indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 4.33 with a descriptive equivalent as very high. This means that, it is always manifested by the English major students. Shown in the result that item no. 3 - thinking of similar words when I encounter obtained a highest mean rating of 4.42 with a descriptive equivalent as very high. This means that, it is always manifested by the English major students across all year levels. While, item no. 1 - trying to find as many ways as I can to use English language accumulated obtained the lowest mean rating of 4.13 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Affective. Also, the fifth indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Shown in the result that item no. 2 - encouraging myself to speak English even when I am afraid of making a mistake obtained the highest mean rating of 4.30 with a descriptive equivalent as very high. This means that, it is always manifested by the English major students. While, item no. 3 - giving myself a reward or treat, when I do well in English obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.76 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Social. Lastly, the sixth indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 4.05 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, the English major students oftentimes manifest it. Shown in the result that item no. 2 - asking English speakers to correct me if I am wrong obtained the highest mean rating of 4.21 with a descriptive equivalent as High. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. While, item no.4 - trying to learn about the culture of English speakers obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.88 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Status of Language Competence

Presented in the table 3 is the status of Language Competence (LC) of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English students across all year levels who were classified as students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Also, the table presented the items that has the highest and the lowest mean rating in each indicator. Moreover, items on each indicator were given a description level from very high to low. On the other hand, each description was given an interpretation which depend upon the level on how English major students certainly manifested language competence across all year levels. To support understanding, the study provided an overall illustration from a comprehensive examination based from data being collected from the participants.

Shown in the table 2.1 is the overall mean rating of language competence which obtained an overall mean rating of 3.82 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Additionally, the variable of the study which is language competence has five indicators such as: reading, writing, speaking, listening, and comprehension.

Reading. In the first indicator, it obtained an overall mean rating of 3.85 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Shown in the result that item no. 5 -reading and understanding academic texts in English obtained the highest mean rating of 4.12 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. While, item no. 4 - comprehending the nuances and figurative language in English texts when reading obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.73 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Writing. The second indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 3.76 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Shown in the result that item no.4 -expressing my ideas and thoughts clearly in written English obtained the highest mean rating of 3.85 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. While, item no. 2 - writing coherently organized paragraphs in English obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.70 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Speaking. Furthermore, the third indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 3.69 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Shown in the result that item no. 5 - participating effectively in English discussions and conversations obtained the highest mean rating of 3.85 with a descriptive equivalent as high.

This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. While, item no. 3 - communicating effectively with narrative speakers of English when speaking obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.47 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Table 2.1. *Statuses of Language Competence*

Variables and Indicators	Mean	Description
A. Reading		
1. Reading English text with no difficulties	3.78	High
2. Understanding most of the vocabulary in English texts	3.75	High
3. Comprehending the nuances and figurative language in English texts when reading.	3.73	High
4. Comprehending the main details of a passage in English materials I read	3.88	High
5. Reading and understanding academic texts in English	4.12	High
Category Mean	3.85	High
B. Writing		
1. Writing grammatically correct sentences in English	3.71	High
2. Writing coherently organized paragraphs in English	3.70	High
3. Writing creatively and expressively in English	3.81	High
4. Expressing my ideas and thoughts clearly in written English	3.85	High
5. Effectively using grammar and vocabulary in writing English sentences	3.74	High
Category Mean	3.76	High
C. Speaking		
1. Speaking English fluently and confidently	3.56	High
2. Expressing my ideas and opinions clearly in English	3.59	High
3. Communicating effectively with narrative speakers of English when speaking.	3.47	High
4. Using appropriate grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation in English	3.64	High
5. Participating effectively in English discussions and conversations	3.69	High
Category Mean	3.59	High
D. Listening		
1. Following English conversations and lectures without difficulty	3.69	High
2. Effectively listening for specific details and main ideas in English	3.94	High
3. Listening and comprehending spoken English in a variety of accents and dialects	3.84	High
4. Understanding complex instructions and directions given in English	3.85	High
5. Listening and comprehending different genres of English speech (news, interviews, presentations, etc.)	3.91	High
Category Mean	3.84	High
E. Comprehension		
1. Understanding English language materials related to my academic field	4.09	High
2. Inferring and interpreting meaning from English texts	3.99	High
3. Understanding English idioms and figurative languages	3.82	High
4. Using dictionaries and other reference materials to comprehend unfamiliar words in English	4.19	High
5. Using context clues to comprehend unknown words in English	4.07	High
Category Mean	4.03	High
Overall Mean	3.82	High

Listening. Also, the fourth indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 3.84, with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Shown in the result that item no. 2 -effectively listening for specific details and main ideas in English obtained the highest mean rating of 3.94, with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. While, the indicator item no. 1 - following English conversations and lectures without difficulty, got the lowest mean of 3.69, with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Comprehension. Lastly, the fifth indicator obtained an overall mean rating of 4.03 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. Shown in the result that item no. 4 - using dictionaries and other reference materials to comprehend unfamiliar words in English obtained the highest mean rating of 4.19 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels. While, item no. 5 - using context clues to comprehend unknown words in English obtained the lowest mean rating of 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that, it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students across all year levels.

Significant Relationship Between Language Learning Strategies and Language Competence of English Major Students

Presented in the table were the results of the study which aimed to examine the significant relationship between language learning strategies and language competence. A thorough examination of data revealed the Language Learning Strategies (LLS) which obtained a category mean of 4.06 with a descriptive equivalent of high in terms of its overall mean rating and Language Competence (LC) which obtained a category mean of 3.82 with a descriptive equivalent of high in terms of its overall mean rating. The Pearson-r illustrates the relationship of language learning strategies and language competence. The researcher measured two parameters in this study. Since the researcher estimated two relationships, the degree of freedom corresponds to the sample size (214) minus 2. Therefore, the $r(212) = .693$ indicates a positive correlation between the two variables. This means that as one variable increase, the other variable tends to increase as well, but the relationship is not perfect. The closer the value to 1, the stronger the correlation between the variables. This can be interpreted that 69% of the variance of language learning strategies and language competence and the remaining 31% is due to other variables not covered in the study. Since, the P-value is less than the significance level of 0.05, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, supporting the conclusion that there is a significant relationship between learning strategies and language competence.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Language Learning Strategies and Language Competence of English Major Students

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Language Learning Strategies	4.06	.693	<.001	Ho Rejected

Lived Experiences of English Major Students on their Language Learning Strategies and Language Competence

There are essential themes were developed from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions of the participants in response to the first research question. Prior to presenting the results from these interviews and discussions, Table 4 outlines the profiles of the participants involved in the qualitative data collection. This table represents the profiles of purposively selected participants who met the inclusion criteria: they must be 1st, 2nd, 3rd, or 4th year English major students at KCAST. The profiles are categorized by the participants' year levels.

Further, Table 4 presents the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of English major students regarding their language learning strategies and language competence. This table summarizes the essential themes that emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses to the first research question. The themes are organized into overarching categories, providing a comprehensive overview of the findings related to how students experience and manage their language learning strategies.

Table 4. The Lived Experiences and Coping Mechanism of English Major Students on their Language Learning Strategies and Language Competence

Issue Probed	Core Ideas	Code/ Categories	Essential Themes	Theoretical Support
Effects of Language Learning Strategies on Communication Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Having conversation and immersion in English to practice speaking skills. Revolving around immersion and engagement in English language. Immersing oneself to speak in English even though not that fluent. Participation in different contexts to enhance oneself. Applying English language in different situations. Making it a habit to become effective speaker. Talking with oneself in front of the mirror. 	<p>Consistent Practice and Immersion</p> <p>Interactive Learning in Diverse Contexts</p> <p>Integration into Daily Life</p>	Immersion and Active Engagement to Practice Communication Skills	Krashen's Input Hypothesis

Effectiveness of Various Language Materials Contributing to Language Competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategies by watching foreign movies to speaking skills. • Watching movies and searching unfamiliar words encountered. • Watching movies and getting into accessible websites to widen vocabulary. • Making reading as a habit to become effective speaker of the language. • Surrounding oneself with English media. • Reading texts from different sources. 	Watching Movies to enrich vocabulary	Deliberate use of Various Forms of Media	Media Ecology Theory
Impact of High-fallutin Words on Language Competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being challenged in learning English when encountering unusual words. • Difficulties in learning various vocabularies. • Difficulty in constructing sentences due to a lack of vocabulary. • Challenges in English when encountering unfamiliar words and having difficulties in pronunciation. • The lack of knowledge and vivid storage of vocabulary. 	Grappling with Unfamiliar Words Lack of clarity and understanding in Language usage	Navigating Difficulties on the Complexity of Vocabulary	Krashen's Input Hypothesis
Impact of Diverse Learning Style and Lack of Resources to Language Competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges to identify learning strategies that suits preferences. • Trying several strategies yet ineffective to identify LLS. • Difficulties in finding effective LLS that aligns the learning style. • Challenges due to the limited resources that caters the learning preference. • Posing challenges in language learning due to resource constraints. 	Trial and Error in Learning Strategies Resource Limitations to align Learning Styles	Dynamic Process of Adaptation and Resilience in Language Learning	Constructivism Theory
Coping Skills in Language Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeking support to overcome difficulties. • Social factors serve a source of encouragement in language learning • Overcoming challenges with advices. • Consulting others to help understand and make decisions. • Seeking assistance in learning applications. • Finding suggestions from other people and internet. • Encouraging oneself to navigate challenges. • Developing a positive mindset towards mistakes. • Conquer the barriers by staying positive, to in develop language competence. 	Social Support and Motivation Seeking Guidance and Assistance Optimism Towards Failures and Difficulties	Proactive Approaches in Leveraging Various Resources Fostering Positive Attitude Amidst Challenges in Language Learning	Bandura's Concept of Modeling on Social Learning Theory Self-efficacy Theory

Immersion and Active Engagements to Practice Communication Skills. In the context of language learning strategies, English major student's experiences are employment of strategies in regards to develop their language competence by having a consistent practice and immersion to the English language. It was mentioned by the participants that consistent practice and immersion to the English language really benefits to enhance effective communication skills and develop their language competence in English language.

Consistent Practice and Immersion. This is the first code of the first probed issue. Some of the participants stated that their consistent practice and immersion as a language learning strategy really have a huge impact to build a development on their language competence which also helps to improve their communication skills. Participants noted that regular engagement with the language helps in retaining vocabulary and grammar more effectively. Hence, this consistent exposure not only improves language skills but also boosts confidence in communication even they are not good enough from English Language since, it can be learned throughout their exposures.

Similarly, Participant 2 recognized the employment as a language learning strategy by immersing themselves in conversations using

the English language. They believed that this kind of strategy is a practice to help develop their language competence in various situations using the English language. Further, they exposed themselves in a context where there is a constant language practice to help the development is rapidly increase. Thus, the participant find immersion and practice of the certain language could be a way to become an effective communicator of the said language. The participant stated that:

“One of the strategies that I’ve learned is to have conversation and immersion and kanang mag use ko og English interactively to practice my speaking skills.” (IDI-002)

(One of the strategies that I’ve learned is to have conversation and immersion, also I use English interactively to practice my speaking skills.)

Also, a participant recognized revolving around immersion and practice through engagement as their language learning strategy, which helps them to develop their skills in language competence. They apply the use of a certain language that they are learning through authentic use such in engagement since, it helps them to keep active within the usage of a certain language in all aspect of which it fosters an effective delivery of communication. Hence, they find it an opportunity to delve more in various conversations using the English language as a way also of practice seeking for enhancement. When Participant 7 stated that:

“My strategies in language learning are revolve around immersion, practice an engagement in English language.” (FGD-002)

(My strategies in language learning revolves around immersion, practice, and engagement in the English language.)

The participant recognized that they make an effort to speak English regularly, even though they are not yet very fluent in the language. They believe that using English in real-life situations helps improve their language skills. By immersing themselves in English, they aim to gain confidence and become more comfortable with the language. The participants take the opportunity also in which they allow themselves to face their fears when using the language, also to explore various things while using the language when speaking or delivering a message in front of many. As what Participant 10 stated that:

“In my case immersing myself to speak in English even though, I am not that fluent.” (FGD-005)

(In my case, I immerse myself in speaking English even though I am not yet fluent.)

Interactive Learning in Diverse Contexts. This is the second code of the first probed issue. The participants imparted statements which focuses on interaction through various contexts to develop themselves in language competence using the target language. Applying the English language in many contexts has a huge impact to grasp enhancement from various speakers of the target language. Also, utilizing English language in academic setting is also an edge to deliver effective ideas when dealing situations such by having an oral report or writing papers. Therefore, this is also such a good technique to maintain development in the target language for the learners.

In connection, a participant is highlighting their commitment in improving their language skills through active class involvement. By regularly participating in class activities and discussions, they aim to strengthen their language competence. This engagement helps them practice and apply language concepts in real-time. They believe that consistent participation is crucial for their growth and fluency. Also, they believe that this approach supports their goal of becoming more proficient in the language. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“In class jod, I always participate to enhance myself in language competence.” (IDI-003)

(In class, I always participate to enhance myself in language competence.)

Likewise, a participant also applies the target language in different situations to help enhance their language competence. This is a notion that students believed that applying the language in various situation from a certain context really helps them to nourish them inputs needed to acquire the language they are learning. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“I apply it in different situations in academic such as reporting or doing my thesis.” (IDI-005)

(I apply this strategy in various academic situations, such as when I am reporting or working on my thesis.)

Integration to Daily Life. This is the third code of the first probed. The participants imparted statements that they include the language that they are learning to an everyday practice. Also, instance such like talking to their oneself in the mirror using the English language. Having this kind of practice makes learners to keep immersed with the language practice making it continuous to develop their language competence all the time.

In connection, a participant employs strategies that makes them practice the language to an everyday use to help enhance their competence over the time. They focus on practicing frequently to enhance their proficiency. Their goal is to become a more efficient and effective speaker of the language. With this, putting the target language as a habit into their daily lives helps them in line with the development throughout their competence as an effective speaker particularly in English. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“Akong strategy sa language learning to enhance my competence, especially sa English is I make it a habit to practice more and become efficient and effective speaker of that certain language.” (IDI-004)

(My strategy in language learning to enhance my competence, especially in English is I make it a habit to practice more and become efficient and effective speaker of that certain language.)

Similarly, a participant also personally talks themselves using the mirror to regulate practice, also to test their ability when speaking the English language. They suggest that there is an alternative way in continuous process to enhance oneself in language competence particularly in speaking. Additionally, they found talking with oneself on the mirror as weird. However, they mostly liked when talking themselves in front of the mirror as a way of practice. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“Then sa speaking, maybe weird pero ganahan ko mag storya sa akong kaugalingon sa mirror mag try-try ko og storya.” (FGD-001)

(Then, for speaking, maybe it is weird, but I like talking to myself in front of the mirror, practicing and trying to speak.)

Deliberate Use of Various Forms of Media. In the context of language learning strategies, English major students usually utilize various materials and media that containing texts related to the language seeking to widen their vocabulary and enhance their language competence in all aspect. Hence, most of the learner’s shared their strategies using the effectiveness of various materials and platforms to learn the English language comprehensively.

Watching Movies to Enrich Vocabulary. This is the first code from the second probed issue. It seems that the participants are fond of watching foreign movies. Most of the movies are source of rich vocabularies which exposes viewers to find meaning of it. Additionally, movies are a great source of how learners understand the words and phrases varied to use in some contexts. Thus, learners spent time watching a movie not just by having an entertainment but doubles its purpose such in learning the English in a wide scope of language which help learners develop their language competence in all aspect.

Further, a participant states that watching movies in a foreign language is one of their strategies for improving their speaking skills. They believe that by listening to native speakers in movies, they can enhance their pronunciation and intonation. This method helps them become more familiar with the natural flow and rhythm of the language. Additionally, it allows them to pick up new vocabulary and phrases in context, making it easier to remember and use them. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“Kuan one of my strategies is that kanang naga watch gani ko og mga movies, kanang ilang language kay foreign language kay maka enhance jod sya saakong kuan pag speak.” (IDI-001)

(One of my strategies is that, I watch movies with foreign language, because it enhances my ability to speak.)

Moreover, the participant highlights that watching movies is their most common method for language learning. They see it as a valuable way to absorb the language, often picking up nuances subconsciously. This approach allows them to learn naturally and effortlessly while being entertained. They consider this method both common and highly effective for making substantial progress in language acquisition. Thus, they believe that watching movies can significantly enhance their language skills. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“The most common factor, I can say that is watching movies. In that way it is an avenue for me to learn the language even though, I am not really learning it consciously but subconsciously and I think that is the common and effective way of having an impact in learning the language.” (IDI-003)

(The most common factor for me is watching movies. This provides an avenue for learning the language, even if it happens subconsciously rather than consciously. I believe this is a common and effective method for making a significant impact on language learning.)

In connection with that, a participant finds that watching movies and accessing various websites are effective methods for expanding their knowledge and vocabulary. As an English major student, these activities provide practical and engaging ways to immerse themselves in the language. They believe that these methods are more accessible and enjoyable compared to traditional study techniques. By regularly engaging with diverse content, they can encounter new words and phrases in context, aiding retention and comprehension. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“Watching movies and getting into accessible websites are much easier to widen my knowledge or vocabulary as an English major student.” (IDI-005)

(Watching movies and accessing various websites are much easier ways for me to broaden my knowledge and vocabulary as an English major student.)

Lastly, the participant used to enjoy watching Thai movies, especially Boys' Love (BL) ones, with subtitles. When they encountered unfamiliar words in the subtitles, they would look them up to learn their meanings. This method allowed them to expand their vocabulary while enjoying content they liked. By doing this, they combined entertainment with education, making the learning process more engaging. This practice helped them improve their language skills in an enjoyable and practical way. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“Sauna po ganahan ko mag watch og Thai movies kanang mga BL in which naa syay kanang mga subtitle then if naay unfamiliar words then akoo tung gina search aron maka tuon ko po.” (FGD-001)

(Before, I enjoyed watching Thai movies, particularly BL ones with subtitles, and whenever there were unfamiliar words, I would search them up to learn.)

Reading a Variety of Texts. Moving on to second code of the second probed issue. In response to the In-depth interviews and focus-grouped discussions, students also utilize various language materials such as text, books and apps related to English language as their strategy to enhance their language competence. Additionally, various materials related to language learning also to improve language competence making learner's to better to comprehend texts, ideas and academic related matters that is written.

Similarly, the participant emphasizes that their primary language learning strategy involves practicing reading regularly. By making reading a habitual activity, they aim to improve their overall competence in English. This practice is seen as a foundational step towards becoming a more efficient and effective speaker. The participant believes that consistent reading will enhance their language skills, including vocabulary and comprehension. Ultimately, they view this method as essential for achieving fluency and proficiency in English. As what Participant 4 stated that:

"Akong strategy sa language learning to enhance my competence especially sa English, I am practicing reading, I make it a habit to practice more and become efficient and effective speaker of that certain language." (IDI-004)

(My strategy in language learning to enhance my competence, especially in English, is by practicing reading. I make it a habit to practice more to become an efficient and effective speaker of that particular language.)

Moreover, a participant recognized a strategy that surrounding oneself with English-language books is an effective method to enhance language competence, as it exposes learners to diverse vocabulary, grammatical structures, and literary styles. Thus, it is essential to learners since, it helps them to familiarize themselves with idiomatic expressions and enhance their understanding of nuanced language usage which are essential components of language proficiency over the time. As what Participant 8 stated that:

"I immerse myself in English language by surrounding myself with English medias, such as reading books." (FGD-002)

(I immerse myself in the English language by surrounding myself with English media, such as reading books.)

In connection with that, a participant recognized that reading various sources including the usage of apps nowadays such as Facebook is also kind of strategy in learning that directs learners to the competency of English language. In this way using the present source is an avenue to them to discover inputs such as new vocabularies that emerges nowadays, helping them to widen their comprehension to various texts, it is a top tier strategy since, they are not just using books but also the famous application nowadays which contains elements related to the medium of English making their lead in developing their competence. As what Participant 8 stated that:

"Also reading texts from different sources most especially from Facebook, because the medium of language that is being used is English language. In that way it is an avenue for me to learn the language." (FGD-003)

(I also read texts from different sources, especially on Facebook, where English is the primary language used. This provides an additional avenue for me to learn the language.)

Navigating Difficulties on the Complexity of Vocabulary. In the context of language learning strategies, learners also experienced difficulties such as encountering unfamiliar words and phrases which could hinders them to enhance their competency in the English language. Therefore, this scenario really impacts their comprehension, application fluency on the target language making it difficult to grasp inputs and information coming from various sources leading to misinterpretation of context or content being utilized while learning the English language.

Grappling with Unfamiliar Words. This is the first code of the third probed issue. Participants reported that the challenge when it terms to learning the English language is dealing with various vocabulary words which deals difficulty on their capacity to comprehend as they have lack of knowledge regarding with the specific word present from the source they are using. Thus, leading to misinterpretation leads to slowing down the capacity of the student's comprehension either on communication or interpretations.

In connection, a participant finds it challenging to learn English due to the frequent encounter with unfamiliar words, which they need to either learn or look up. They also struggle with achieving fluency in the language, which means they feel their speaking and comprehension skills are not yet advanced. They acknowledge that this is a common part of the learning process and recognize that they still have more to learn. The participant understands that becoming fluent takes time and ongoing effort. As what Participant 6 stated that:

"For me siguro, the hardest challenge that I had faced in learning English is kanang there are many unusual words that I need to learn pa or I need to search and then one thing pod also is that I am not that fluent pa lang. Just like what they have said there is still learning pa pod." (FGD-001)

(For me, perhaps the hardest challenge I have faced in learning English is encountering many unfamiliar words that I still need to learn or search for. Another thing is that I'm not yet fluent. Just like what they have said, there is still more learning ahead.)

Similarly, when encountering unfamiliar vocabularies yet a learner does not tempt to seek the meaning of the word, a tendency that

there will be difficulties in enhancing one's language competence. Learner's role is crucial when it terms to language learning, since there are various vocabularies that indeed need to achieve in order to effectively equip themselves such in comprehending various contexts. Thus, even if the learners used varieties of resources in the target language but neglecting the essence to get some inputs of it will be useless. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“So, one of my challenges nga na encounter kay kuan ang pag expand sa akoang vocabulary, it is true na ganahan ko mutan aw og mga movies og mag read og mga books. Pero pag naa koy ma encounter na kuan lisod sya na vocabularies, dili man gud nako sya gina kuan search kung unsay meaning ana maong kuan mag lisod jod ko.” (FGD-002)

(So, one of the challenges I encounter is expanding my vocabulary. It is true that I enjoy watching movies and reading books. But when I encounter difficult vocabularies, it is like I don't really search for their meanings, which makes it really difficult for me.)

Lack of Clarity and Understanding in Language Usage. This is second code of the third probed issue. The participants stated that there are limitations when crafting their writings due to the lack of clarity about the words they are meant to use in the specific sentence to convey their ideas. Also, when encountering unfamiliar words yet they do not know the specific pronunciation to be exact. The most crucial is when having the lack of knowledge to the target language they tend to learn, also the limit storage of vocabularies from the learners. Thus, this issue leads to create limiting the learner's ability in expressing their ideas since, there is an existing presence of lacking when it terms to the clarity in the actual usage of the vocabulary to the context of the language.

In connection, the participant is concerned that using complex or unfamiliar words without understanding their meaning may makes them limit in conversation. They feel that their ability to construct sentences is limited by their lack of knowledge about these highfalutin words. The participant highlighted that this lack of understanding can lead to use the words incorrectly, which affects their confidence and effectiveness in communication. As a result, they tend to use simpler language to avoid making mistakes. As what Participant 9 stated that:

“Most probably the limit of words na magamit nako throughout saakong sentence or phrasing if mag gamit ko og high fallutin words on the spot and wala ko kabalo sa meaning mura ralog mag mukhang bobo ko ba on the spot. Gamit-gamit unya wala kabalo unsay meaning so limited kasagaran akong ma use na words in terms of constructing my sentences.” (FGD-004)

(Most probably, the limit of words I can use in my sentence or phrasing if I use highfalutin words on the spot without knowing their meaning, I would appear foolish on the spot. I use them without knowing their meaning, so most of the time, I am limited in the words I can use in constructing my sentences.)

Moreover, a participant finds it difficult to learn English when faced with unfamiliar words and pronunciation issues. They admitted that they feel a sense of insecurity when they cannot pronounce words correctly. Hence, this struggle is compounded by a fear of being judged or criticized by others. The participant's concern about how they are perceived affects their confidence in using English. As a result, they may hesitate to practice or use the language in public settings. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“The most challenging for me when it comes to English is when you are encountering unfamiliar words and the moment that you cannot pronounce it properly, since I am afraid of judgements from other people.” (IDI-001)

(The most challenging aspect of learning English for me is encountering unfamiliar words and struggling with pronunciation, as I am afraid of being judged by others.)

Lastly, a participant finds that, as an English major, one significant challenge they face is a lack of prior knowledge about the target language. This gap in knowledge leads to a limited vocabulary compared to others who may be more experienced. They acknowledge that having a broader vocabulary is crucial for effective communication and understanding. Hence, the participant feels that improving language skills requires addressing this gap in vocabulary and knowledge. As what Participant 10 stated that:

“Siguro para sakoa the challenges as an English major, kanang lack of knowledge kasi wala kay koy knowledge about kanang language, then dili kaayo wide akong vocabulary as what they have said English.” (FGD-005)

(Perhaps, as an English major, one of the challenges I may face is the lack of prior knowledge about the language then I do not have the wide vocabulary as what they have said English.)

Dynamic Process of Adaptation and Resilience in Language Learning. In the context of language learning strategies of the students, usually they are experiencing to have difficulties when it terms to the strategies that aligns with their learning style, also the lack of materials which are suitable for them in learning the English language effectively particularly in enhancing their language competence in all aspect. Thus, most of the students shared their difficulties in choosing appropriate learning styles and resources fit to their learning preference better for enhancing their language competence.

Trial and Error in Learning Strategies. This is the first code of the fourth probed issue. Students reported that they are having a hard time when seeking strategies that aligns their learning preference. Hence, they cannot proceed in the learning process without having the trial-and-error test in which it allows them to identify their preferred learning approach in relation to develop their language competence.

In that sense, the participant faces challenges in discovering effective language learning strategies that align with their personal preferences. They experience a process of trial and error, trying different approaches to see what works best for them. This ongoing experimentation is aimed at improving their overall language competence. Hence, the participant acknowledges that finding the right methods is essential for their progress that will effectively enhance their language skills and fit their individual learning style. what Participant 2 stated that:

“The challenges kay mag include siya og trial and error to identify what suits our learning strategies aligning strategies that suits my preference seeking to enhance my language competence.” (IDI-002)

(The challenges include engaging in trial and error to identify learning strategies that suit my preferences while seeking to enhance my language competence.)

Similarly, the participant has experimented with various strategies for learning English, but they have not found these methods to be successful. To address this, they are adopting a trial-and-error approach, trying different techniques until they find one that works best for them. This process involves testing various methods and evaluating their effectiveness. Thus, the participant is committed to finding the most effective way to learn the language through persistent experimentation. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“I have tried several strategies before and I have not seen it as effective that is why I need to apply the trial and error, until such time I have found the most suitable way in learning the language.” (IDI-004)

(I have tried several strategies before, but they have not been very effective. That’s why I need to apply a trial-and-error approach until I find the most suitable way to learn the language.)

Resource Limitations to Align Learning Styles. This is the second code of the probed issue. Students usually stated that there are limited resources when it terms in catering their various learning styles, making it difficult to align with their preference. Limited resources catering to diverse learning styles can hinder the effectiveness of language learning by failing to address the learner’s needs adequately. This difficulty may lead to certain students unable to fully engage with the material, impeding their language competence. To optimize language learning outcomes, it is crucial for educational institutions to invest in a variety of resources that accommodate diverse learning styles, fostering inclusivity and maximizing student success.

In connection with that, a participant struggles to find effective language learning strategies that fit their visual learning style. They find that traditional resources often focus on auditory or verbal methods, which do not align with their preference for visual learning. This mismatch makes it challenging for them to find suitable materials that cater to their needs. Hence, they are seeking or to adapt materials that match their visual learning approach to improve their language learning. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“Kaning, difficulties na ma encounter kay kaning finding effective language learning strategies that aligns my learning style that is the primarily visual, kay I am a visual learner and I find traditional language resources often focus on auditory or verbal instruction making it challenging to find resources that often cater to my preferred learning style as visual learner.” (FGD-002)

(Encountering difficulties in finding effective language learning strategies that aligns with my primarily visual learning style. Traditional language resources often emphasize auditory or verbal instruction, making it harder to find materials that cater to my preference for visual learning as a visual learner.)

Similarly, the participant prefers learning through auditory methods, as they find this approach most effective. They face a challenge due to a lack of sufficient resources that cater to their auditory learning style. Although they believe auditory methods help them learn better, the available resources are not adequate to support this preference. Additionally, the learner keeps motivated when the resources was aligned with its learning style, since it is convenient to grasp information regarding the target language and make improvements to its language competence: As what Participant 9 stated that:

“Akoa kay preferred learning style man gud nako ang auditory na mas makatuon ko and ang challenges na akoang na encounter is dili enough ang resources gani na ganahn ko personally mutoon kay mas effective sya sakoa if auditory but the resources are not enough.” (FGD-004)

(My preferred learning style is actually auditory, as I find it more effective for me to learn that way. However, the challenge I encounter is the lack of sufficient resources that I personally prefer, as I find auditory methods more effective for my learning, but unfortunately, the resources available are insufficient.)

Consequently, a participant also recognized the difficulty in learning due to a lack of resources that implements the learner’s learning style. The difficulty highlighted that it is insufficient to learn the input by only using the auditory style of learning since, the learner emphasized that both auditory and visual should be integrated in order to grasp the information needed to learn the target language. Hence, if one of these preferences could lack in the utilization of the learning process will have an impact, making it ineffective to learn the language and impedes the enhancement of language competence. As what Participant 10 stated that:

“I am both visual and auditory dili lang kay mutan aw lang ko makasabot ko dayun dpat makit-an sad nako at the same time maka dungog ko. So, in my case kay siguro mga difficulties na akong na encounter sa pag implement effective language learning strategies

kay kuan kulang pod og resources.” (FGD-010)

(I am both visual and auditory. I do not just understand by seeing alone thus I need to see and hear at the same time. So, in my case the difficulties I might encounter in implementing effective language learning strategies could be due to a lack of resources.)

Proactive Approaches in Leveraging Various Resources. In the context of language learning particularly in developing one’s language competence, there are various challenges that can demotivate students to learn. It is crucial for them to seek support amidst the difficulties from their peers, family and other people who could make influence with them in order to gain encouragements in learning the target language effectively. Thus, students provided their coping mechanism amidst these difficulties by highlighting the social factors as their approach to reinforcements which has a huge role to make a positive impact towards their learning helping to achieve development in language competence.

Social Support and Motivation. This is the first code of the sixth probed issue. Students reported that social factors had a significant role in relation to cope with their difficulties in language learning. Learners, seek assistance from their instructors, friends and even their family members with the concepts they find difficult in order for them to understand it even better, also they seek support from them to encourage and motivate their minds to learn the language effective effectively amidst the difficulties they are facing.

In connection with that, students recognized the role of social factors in terms of giving them with much support to deal with the things they cannot do with themselves. Hence, offering much support to the learners leads to achievement of the learning process of the language. Additionally, this would able learners to stick motivated amidst the possible hurdles they might face during their learning of the target language, possible to the pavement of success. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“The coping mechanism that helps me to overcome those challenges is, I like to be surrounded with people na ganahan pod og Especially, sa mga instructors na mag hatag og advices na kanang mag basa2 jod daw and then mas mag learn og mga grammar.” (FGD-001)

(The coping mechanism that helps me overcome these challenges is being surrounded by people who also enjoy English, especially with instructors who provide advice emphasizing the importance of reading and learning grammar thoroughly.)

Moreover, the participant relies on their peers, particularly family and friends, for support when facing challenges. Whenever they encounter difficulties, they cannot manage on their own, they reach out to friends for assistance. Their friends and family provide help and guidance, making the challenges more manageable. This support system is crucial for the participant's ability to overcome obstacles. Thus, they value the assistance and encouragement they receive from their close social circle. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“Akoang makuan is, I am seeking support from my peers especially sakong family, my friends because everytime na naa koy kanang dili kaya muduol jod ko sakong friends and then ginatabangan pod ko nila pod.” (FGD-002)

(I seek support from my peers, especially my family and friends, as whenever I encounter challenges that I cannot handle alone, I always tap to my friends for help, and they also assist me with it.)

The participant believes that friends play a significant role in motivating them to learn English. These friends provide encouragement and support, which helps them stay motivated despite the challenges of learning a new language. The presence of supportive friends can make the learning process more enjoyable and less daunting. Further, social support helps them to continue their language studies and improve their competence. Hence, friends are a crucial factor in their language learning journey, offering both motivation and assistance. As what Participant 8 stated that:

“There are factors like friends that could motivate you to learn and cope those challenges in continuing to learn the language and enhance your competence.” (FGD-003)

(There are factors, such as friends, that can motivate you to learn and help you cope with the challenges of continuing to learn the language and enhance your competence.)

Fostering Positive Attitude Amidst Challenges in Language Learning. In the context of language learning students might face possible challenges and difficulties in finding strategies and development of their competence particularly in English language. Thus, amidst those hurdles learners always make their pave to cope those challenges and difficulties in achieving success, by believing from their selves in such of having a positive mindset, which eliminates all the negativities. Possessing optimist outlook has an important role for every individual as it fosters resilience and growth in solving problems within oneself. Additionally, leading to improved their capability and greater success to develop their language competence amidst difficulties.

Optimism Towards Failures and Difficulties. This is the second code of the sixth probed issue. Students always face failures as well as difficulties with regards in learning and developing their competence in the specific target language. Hence, being optimist amidst these problems is an edge to disregard the hurdles that will hinder their success., Additionally, with this attitude in practice learners may learn also to manage themselves, also this will increase their motivation that opens for opportunities in enhancing their competence to the target language.

In connection with that, a student recognized the pivotal role of giving encouragement to oneself in the midst of challenges. This

positive attitude fosters courage to conquer the odds along the way of learning and developing their language competence. Thus, this fosters a positive mindset towards negativities which will eliminate instances that will block the learner in developing and learning the language. As what Participant 8 stated that:

“I will give encouragement to myself that you need this specific matter, because need to agihan nimo sya ba, you need to take that path for you to take your journey. In that way that could motivate you to learn and cope those challenges in continuing to learn the language and enhance your competence.” (FGD-003)

(I will give myself with the encouragement needed for this specific matter, because you need to conquer it, you need to take that path for your journey. This can motivate you to learn and overcome challenges in continuing to learn and enhance your competence.)

Moreover, a student also recognized having a positive mindset towards mistakes rather than seeing it as a failure. This enables I to learn out from their mistakes and improve what they can do for better development. Hence, it will eliminate discouragement towards failures, seeking for more opportunities without the feeling of fear in the development of their competence, since there is no such one thing that a learner could not know without experiencing a mistake. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“Often involve developing a positive mindset towards mistakes. Instead of seeing errors as failures, I myself view it as valuable learning opportunities. This mindset kay mag shift siya to foster resilience and a willingness to take risks in language use.” (IDI-005)

(Often involves cultivating a positive mindset towards mistakes. Instead of viewing errors as failures, I personally see them as valuable learning opportunities. This mindset can shift to promote resilience and a willingness to take risks in language use.)

Similarly, a participant also recognized the role of positivity to the challenges, since this can conquer barriers that hinders its success in developing their competence in the target language. Hence, this also helps them to engage in various contexts which has an impact in the way to learn the language also helping them to recognize their improvements in the language in relation to their growth. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“I can conquer barriers by staying positive and reach higher levels in proficiency when using English. It helps me to improve in such a way that it boosts my confident in participating various classroom activities, most especially on oral recitation and as well in written those coping strategies help me to evaluate if there is a progress or not and implementing those specific strategies, in that way it helps me flexible in language competence.” (FGD-002)

(I can conquer barriers by staying positive and reaching higher levels of proficiency in English. This improvement boosts my confidence in participating in various classroom activities, especially oral recitations and written assignments. These coping strategies help me evaluate my progress and, by implementing them, I become more flexible in my language competence.)

Insights Shared of English Major Students with Regards to the Effectiveness of Language Learning Strategies to their Language Competence

Presented in Table 5 are the responses of the participants regarding to their insights to the effectivities of language learning strategies in enhancing their language competence. There are five essential themes which are drawn out from the in-depth and focus group discussion of the participants for the second question. The essential themes consisted codes based from the issues being probed which are summarized in the table.

Table 5. Insights of English Major Students with Regards to the Effectiveness of Language Learning Strategies in Developing Language Competence

Issue Probed	Core Ideas	Code/ Categories	Essential Themes	Theoretical Support
Effects of Language Learning Strategies on Communication Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Succes in expressing ideas and opinions even better. • Strategies help become more comfortable when expressing thoughts. 	Self-awareness and Comfort in enhanced Expression of Ideas and Opinions	Benefits of Language Learning Strategies	Cognitive Theory
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Articulates thoughts clearly and conveys ideas, and enhancing overall language competence. • Language learning strategies enhances one’s ability to construct well-structured sentences and effective communication. 	Improving Language Competence		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The role of language learning is significant for learners to express thoughts and ideas easier. 	Essential Role in Developing Communication Skills	Vital Role of Language Learning in Communication	Communicative Competence Theory

Effects of fostering Language Learning Strategies in Developing Language Competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective strategies help English major students improve their communication skills. • Language learning strategies are crucial, especially for communication skills. • Fosters proficiency in various aspects in enriching language development. • Improves English-speaking skills on how to properly pronounce the words. • Awareness on what should be improved and learn more to widen the knowledge. • Provides techniques necessary to improve language competence in all aspects. • Crucial in the role of development, improving grammar and vocabulary. 	Awareness & Enhancement of Language Proficiency through application	Impact of LLS on Language Proficiency and Development	Constructivism Theory
Factors in Language Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is very significant to rely on someone who give corrections towards mistake. • External factors by receiving suggestions from the things who might not learned yet. • External factors foster motivation which learning the language will boost more. • External factors play a significant impact in developing strategies. • Embracing mistakes to help oneself in improvements. • Treating challenges as helpful obstacles in helping to determine the strengths and weaknesses. • Desire for personal and academic growth, while pushing oneself to learn. • Conditioning oneself. Hence, everything will be learned in process. 	Importance of Support and Feedback in Language Learning	Influence of External Factors on Language Learning and Competence	Social Learning Theory
		Role of External Factors in Motivation and Support		
		Embracing Mistakes and Challenges for Personal Growth	Personal Growth and Development in English Language through Resilience and Self-Directed Learning	Self-determination Theory
		Intrinsic Motivation for Personal and Academic Growth		

Benefits of Language Learning Strategies. The insights of English major students in accordance to the effectiveness of language learning strategies in developing their language competence. Based from the information given by the participants, it is claimed that students should recognized the self- awareness and comfort in enhancing the expression of ideas and opinions as benefit of language learning strategies in developing their language competence in all aspect.

Self-awareness and Comfort in enhanced Expression of Ideas and Opinions. This is the first code of the first probed issue. With the help of language learning strategies, learners are aware in the articulation of their ideas whether it is effective or not. Participants are mindful of the thoughts they are using especially, when delivering messages in many contexts. This helps them particularly in assessing themselves whether they deliver the messages effectively and efficient. Thus, having this aspect as a learner paves clarity in understanding one's own perspectives, allowing to articulate expression of ideas and opinions, while comfort cultivates confidence in sharing them openly, enriching communication and fostering constructive dialogue.

In connection with that, a participant recognized the role of strategies in learning the language, especially by having their awareness and comfortability when expressing their ideas clearly. Hence, it is a great help for them to articulate their ideas effectively, especially when expressing their opinions towards other since, they can regulate errors that they could generate when delivering messages making it clear to the audience. Additionally, this paves a way to avoid misinterpretations and further mistakes which enriches their expression of ideas constructively. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Naga help sya kay kanang, through this is mas ma express akong ideas and opinions even better.” (IDI-002)

(It helps me so that I can express my ideas and opinions even better.)

The participant believes that using different strategies can help them understand themselves better, particularly in how they express their thoughts. By experimenting with various methods, they can identify which approaches make them feel more comfortable and

confident in communication. This self-awareness can lead to more effective and natural expression of ideas. Understanding their preferred strategies also helps them tailor their learning process to suit their individual needs. Overall, discovering the best strategies for themselves enhances their ability to communicate comfortably and effectively. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“Strategies would really help you to know yourself even more, in what way to become more comfortable when expressing your thoughts.” (IDI-003)

(Strategies can truly help you understand yourself better, particularly in finding ways to become more comfortable when expressing your thoughts.)

Improving Language Competence. This is the second code of the first probed issue. In the aspect of strategies in language learning students shared its essential impact towards the development of their language competence in all aspect especially, in communication. Additionally, these strategies build the learners foundation to use the target language constructively in many contexts which leads the path towards their academic success and growth as an individual Hence, this will help learners to delve the language, exploring to gain inputs and apply their learnings through academic or social interactions.

Moreover, a participant recognized the ability to express their thoughts clearly and effectively to convey their ideas. Additionally, these strategies in language learning are essentially designed to contribute in improving their overall language skills and competence. Essentially, the learner’s competency in articulating thoughts and conveying ideas is viewed as a significant factor in enhancing their overall language ability making it to essentially deliver effective communication in many contexts. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Kuan maka articulate og thoughts more clearly and it analyzes complex concept as well as convey ideas, ultimately enhancing the overall language competence para mas dali masabtan which is maka cause siya og effective communication.” (IDI-002)

(It can articulate thoughts clearly and it analyzes complex concepts as well as convey ideas, ultimately in enhancing the overall language competence in order to comprehend easily in which a factor of an effective communication.)

Consequently, a participant highlighted that when utilizing language learning strategies, it helps learners in understanding the rules of grammar and syntax. By employing these strategies, learners are better equipped to comprehend the structure and framework of the target language, including its grammatical rules and sentence formation. Thus, understanding forms a solid foundation, which in turn it improves their capability to construct sentences that are both grammatically accurate and well-structured. Also, language competency enhances their ability to communicate effectively in the language they are learning. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“Language learning strategies help me to grasp the rules of grammar and syntax. A strong foundation in these aspects it enhances my ability to construct grammatically correct and well-structured sentences, facilitating effective communication.” (IDI-005)

(Language learning strategies help me grasp the rules of grammar and syntax. A strong foundation in these areas enhances my ability to construct grammatically correct and well-structured sentences, facilitating effective communication.)

Vital Role of Language Learning in Communication. In the point of view of the students particular in language learning especially who utilizes strategies, it is claimed that it is the solid foundation of competence in the target language. Hence, this paves a path to achieve success in communication. Effective communication through language competence opens a various opportunity for learners in engaging the society, since they have the capacity to convey and reciprocate. In this context language learning strategies deal a major role in shaping the learner’s ability to communicate efficiently and effectively.

Essential Role in Developing Communication Skills. This is the first code of the second probed issue. In this aspect language learning strategies deal an essential role to develop language competence which also serves to achieve the effectiveness of communication skills of the learners. Hence, learners have the capacity of competency of the language, it serves the communication by enabling learners to effectively convey ideas, emotions, and information in all aspect of their skills and across cultural and linguistic barriers.

In connection with that, the participant emphasizes the importance of language learning strategies in enhancing language competence, especially in the context of expressing ideas effectively. They highlight that these strategies are particularly beneficial for English major students, aiding in the improvement of vocabulary, grammar, syntax, and overall communication skills. Hence, employing effective strategies, they can articulate their thoughts clearly, coherently, and persuasively in both spoken and written English. Thus, advancing their language competency and academic success. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“Language learning strategies are really essential for developing language competence particularly when expressing ideas effectively, so effective strategies really help us English major students in improving our vocabulary grammar, syntax, and communication skills because it enables us to articulate our thoughts clearly coherently and persuasively in both spoken and written English.” (FGD-002)

(Language learning strategies are crucial for developing language competence, especially when it comes to expressing ideas effectively. For English major students, effective strategies are essential for improving vocabulary, grammar, syntax, and communication skills. They enable us to articulate our thoughts clearly, coherently, and persuasively in both spoken and written English.)

Similarly, the participant underscores the importance of language learning, particularly in the aspect of expressing ideas. They suggest that without knowledge of a specific language, individuals may struggle to interact with others and convey their own thoughts

effectively. Essentially, learners highlighted how language competence is crucial for meaningful communication and engagement with others, as it enables learners to express themselves and engage in conversations more fluently and accurately. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“The role of language learning is such a significant role para sa toa learners, because especially if mag-express tag ideas kay if you do not know that specific language mag-lisod ka ug interact with other people and if mag-express ka ug mga own thoughts nmo murag naa kay difficulties diraa po na part.” (FGD-001)

(The role of language learning is highly significant for learners because especially when expressing ideas, if you do not know that specific language, it can be difficult for you to interact with other people and express your own thoughts. You may encounter difficulties in that area.)

Consequently, a participant emphasizes the importance of language learning strategies for students. They highlight that these strategies provide effective ways to learn and remember new language skills, especially in communication by improving understanding and boosting confidence, particular methods play a crucial role in their overcoming language-related challenges. The participant believes that with the right strategies, students can achieve better language proficiency which can enhance their ability can positively impact various areas of their lives. As what Participant 10 stated that:

“The language learning strategies po are really essential good. Labaw na sa toa students, because it will provide effective ways to acquire and retain new language skills. More specially, sa communication skills. Makatabang gyud sya even ma-enhance atong understanding, also mag-boost atong confidence and last is maka-overcome tag mga challenges in some aspects atong life.” (FGD-005)

(The language learning strategies are truly essential, especially for us students, as it offers effective methods to acquire and retain new language skills, particularly in communication. They can greatly help enhance our understanding and boost our confidence, and ultimately help us overcome challenges in various aspects of our live.)

Impact of Language Learning Strategies on Language Proficiency and Development. In the context of language learning strategies, especially learners who utilizes it in enhancing competence it explores how those technique brings significant changes on their development. Hence, it is crucial for learners to utilize various strategies to determine their strengths and weaknesses with regards in the language. In this phase participants shared their insights on how language learning strategies significantly contributed various profound improvement on their language competency in all aspect.

Awareness and Enhancement of Language Proficiency. This is the second code of the second probed issue. In this phase students emphasize the use of strategies in language learning as to help enhance their proficiency on the target language. Thus, proficiency open doors for opportunities and academic success of the learners. Also, it empowers learners to use the language accurately and confidently, making it to actively participate in academic pursuits and social exchanges, facilitating the clarity of delivering the ideas into meaningful interactions.

Moreover, the participant is referring to the benefits of engaging in activities or practices that enhance language skills. The participant believes that such activities help in mastering correct grammar structures, which is fundamental for clear communication. Additionally, it also helps in expanding their vocabulary, allowing them for more precise and varied expression and enriching their language development making them more proficient in using the language effectively. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“It fosters proficiency in various aspects such as creating correct grammar structures, widens my vocabulary and communication overall, it enriches my language development.” (IDI-002)

(It fosters proficiency in various aspects, such as creating correct grammar structures, expanding my vocabulary, and improving overall communication. This, in turn, enriches my language development.)

In connection with that, a participant recognized that utilizing a particular strategy has a significant positive effect on their English-speaking skills. It suggests that this method helps learners to properly pronounce words, particularly those that are unfamiliar or new to them. Thus, the participant is indicating that this approach serves as a helpful guide for improving pronunciation and overall English proficiency. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“Kuan, it improves and have a huge impact in my English-speaking skills, since it serves for me para ma guide ko on how to properly pronounce the words, especially the unfamiliar words which are new for me.” (IDI-001)

(It improves and has a huge impact on my English-speaking skills, since it serves as a guide for me to properly pronounce words, especially the unfamiliar ones which are new to me.)

Furthermore, a participant recognized that strategy helps them become more aware of areas needing for improvement and assist them in expanding their knowledge base. Students emphasize the importance of applying the language across various contexts encountered in daily life, indicating a desire for practical and flexibility of their language skills. Thus, it highlights the value of self-awareness, continuous learning, and real-life application in their pursuit of language proficiency. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“That strategy really helps me to become more aware of the things that I need to improve and learn more to widen my knowledge in applying the language in every context that I deal every day.” (IDI-004)

(That strategy really helps me become more aware of the areas I need to improve and the things I need to learn. It also helps me broaden my knowledge and apply the language effectively in every context I encounter daily.)

Impact on Language Competence and Development. This is the fourth code of the second probed issue. Students highlights how language learning strategies influences learner’s linguistic abilities and overall growth. It encompasses understanding how language competence shapes their knowledge to the certain of the target language. Furthermore, it may involve assessing how language development contributes to broader cognitive, social, and cultural aspects of every learner. Thus, it indicates a comprehensive investigation into the effects of language learning on both competency and personal development.

In connection with that, a participant recognizes the crucial role of language learning strategies in their development as an English major student. They highlight how these strategies equip them with the essential tools and techniques needed to enhance language competence across various skills, including reading, writing, speaking, and listening. By effectively employing these strategies, the participant expresses that they can articulate ideas more clearly and participate in academic discussions with greater confidence, contributing to their overall growth and success in their English studies. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“Language learning strategies have a significant impact on my development as an English major student it is because, they provide with the tools and techniques necessary to improve my language competence in all aspects like, reading, writing, speaking and listening. By employing these strategies, I can express my ideas more clearly and engage in academic discourse more confidently.” (FGD-002)

(Language learning strategies have a significant impact on my development as an English major student. They provide me with the tools and techniques necessary to improve my language competence in all aspects, such as reading, writing, speaking, and listening. By employing these strategies, I can express my ideas more clearly and engage in academic discourse more confidently.)

Similarly, a participant emphasizes the vital role of language learning strategies in their development as an English major student. Additionally, the participant notes that despite initial challenges with grammar, the consistent use of language learning strategies has led to noticeable improvement. Also, it highlights that their vocabulary has expanded significantly through continuous learning, enabling them to utilize a wider range of words in their communication. Overall, the participant underscores how language learning strategies have positively impacted their language skills and overall development. As what Participant 9 stated that:

“As an English major student language learning strategies plays a much crucial role in my development, because it helps me in terms of effective communication delivering my words my phrases in every aspect in communicating directly and more effectively and parehas sa giiningon niya na di paman ko kabalo sauna og grammar but ever since naga gamit kog language learning strategies my grammar started to improve and in terms sa vocabulary the more mag learn ko mas daghan og vocabulary ang magamit nko.” (FGD-004)

(As an English major student, language learning strategies play a crucial role in my development because they help me in terms of effective communication, delivering my words and phrases in every aspect of communication more directly and effectively. Similar to what they said, I didn’t used to know much about grammar before, but ever since I started using language learning strategies, my grammar has started to improve. In terms of vocabulary, the more I learn, the more vocabulary I can use.)

Influence of External Factors on Language Learning and Competence. This is one of the essential themes from the responses of the participants insights coming from the In-depth interviews and focused group discussion being conducted with the categories of importance of support and feedback in language learning and Role of External Factors in Motivation and Support. The participants mentioned how the external factors that influences the learners on their language learning building their competence on the particular target language.

Importance of Support and Feedback in Language Learning. This is the first code of the third probed issue. In-depth interview and FGD participants imparted some of their insights about the importance of support and feedback in language learning. In the context of having a support and feedback to language learning it plays a crucial role in language learning by providing learners with guidance, encouragement, and correction. In addition, constructive feedback helps learners identify and rectify mistakes, leading to improved competence. Further, supportive environments foster confidence and motivation, essential elements for sustained language learning and fluency.

Consequently, a participant recognized the importance of external factors by giving a support and corrections towards learning the language. With that, having someone dependable to provide assistance with aspects like grammar, pronunciation, and contextual language use. Hence, learners seek guidance and correction from this person to improve their language skills effectively. Essentially, it emphasizes the significance of having a reliable source of support and feedback in their language learning journey. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“As a learner, it is very significant to have someone to rely on when doing some corrections towards my grammar, pronunciation or how this to be used in a certain context.” (IDI-003)

(As a learner, it is very important to have someone to rely on for corrections in grammar, pronunciation, and usage in different contexts.)

Similarly, a participant viewed external factors as significant influence on their language learning process. The learners acknowledge the support of teachers, classmates, and other resources in providing suggestions and guidance, particularly in areas they have not mastered yet. With that, it suggests that they value external input and support as integral components of their language learning journey, highlighting the importance of seeking assistance from various sources to enhance their proficiency. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“My perception about external factors, they have many contributions in learning the certain language, for example when I used to get suggestions from my teachers as well as classmates and especially to the things, I may not learn yet.” (IDI-004)

(My perception of external factors is that they contribute significantly to learning a language. For example, getting suggestions from teachers and classmates helps me learn things I may not yet understand.)

Role of External Factors in Motivation and Support. This is the second code of the fourth probed issue. Students imparted their insights about the importance of external factors that provides motivation and support towards the success in learning the language. In addition, encouragement from teachers, peers, and access to resources, play a pivotal role in motivating language learners. Supportive environments foster a sense of community and provide valuable feedback, enhancing learner’s confidence and commitment in learning the target language. These external influences contribute significantly to learner’s motivation and success in mastering the target language.

In connection with that, a participant emphasizes the significant role of instructors, classmates, and friends as the primary motivators in language learning. They suggest that with support from these individuals, learners are more encouraged to engage in language learning activities, especially when these individuals are actively involved and supportive. This support and motivation boost learners’ self-confidence and determination to further improve their language competence. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“Ang biggest factor jud kay atong instructor or atong classmates or atong friends. So, with those factors, it can help us to motivate ourselves. Labi na if kana lang ang support nila nga magtuon jud about language learning. So, by that, with that motivation and with their help, mag-boost ang atong self na mas magtuon pa.” (FGD-001)

(The biggest factor really is our instructor, classmates, or friends. With their support, it can help us motivate ourselves, especially if their support is focused on studying language learning. So, with that motivation and with their help, it boosts our self to study even more.)

Similarly, the participant perceives that their circle of friends, classmates, and instructors are the greatest factors influencing their language learning. Since, their social connections provide support, encouragement, and practical help, which are crucial for developing effective learning strategies. Further, their friends and classmates offer a collaborative environment where they can practice and improve together also, their instructors play a significant role by structured learning. Hence, these factors significantly impact their ability to learn the language and develop competence. As what Participant 8 stated that:

“It perceives me that somehow the greatest factor is the circle of friends as well as classmates and somehow the instructor and these factors plays a significant impact to the learning of language especially in developing the strategies towards the competence.” (FGD-003)

(I perceive that the greatest factors in learning a language are the circle of friends, classmates, and instructors. These factors play a significant role in developing effective strategies and enhancing language competence.)

Personal Growth and Development in English Language through Resilience and Self-Directed Learning. In the context of language learning particular to enhance language competence, learners are fostered through resilience, which enable them to overcome challenges and setbacks. In addition, self-directed learning empowers learners to take ownership of their language learning process, leading to continuous improvement and competence. The participants provided their insights which are the vital component of this theme.

Embracing Mistakes and Challenges for Personal Growth. This is the first code of the third probed issue. With that, embracing mistakes and challenges in language learning is significant as it fosters resilience and a growth mindset, encouraging learners to persist and learn from their mistakes. Thus, when confronting difficulties, learners not only build confidence but also develop a deeper understanding of the language, ultimately enhancing their language competence and proficiency through continuous learning and improvement.

Moreover, a participant reflects on feeling embarrassed when faced with challenging situations in language learning despite of that it was being learned to acknowledge the overcoming these challenges as an essential part of personal development. Learners recognize that making mistakes is a crucial aspect of the learning journey, as it provides valuable experience and opportunities for growth. By embracing these mistakes, they aim to improve their ability to handle and express themselves effectively, particularly in academic contexts. As what Participant 8 stated that:

“As far as I experienced, handling the situation makes me embarrassed, but somehow in the long run, I had realized that it is a part of the development maybe it charges experience, but later on, I am trying to fight that towards myself, because embracing those mistakes could help me in improving myself, especially in handling and expressing ideas in specific matter or context.” (FGD-003)

(As far as I have experienced, handling such situations can be embarrassing. However, in the long run, I have realized that it is part of personal development. These experiences contribute to growth, and later on, I try to confront them. Embracing these mistakes can help me improve, especially in handling and expressing ideas in specific matters or contexts.)

Similarly, a participant indicates that they approach challenges in language learning with a positive mindset, viewing them as opportunities rather than obstacles. The learners perceive these challenges as helpful in identifying their strengths and weaknesses, ultimately aiding in their language learning journey. With that, taking challenges as opportunities for self-assessment and improvement, they demonstrate resilience and a proactive attitude towards their language learning process. As what Participant 9 stated that:

“I handle it not differently that kind of challenges, the moment that I tend to learn I take these challenges as I treat them not as a challenge but rather helpful obstacles that will help me in determining my strengths and weaknesses in learning languages.” (FGD-004)

(I handle these challenges by treating them not as obstacles, but as helpful opportunities that help me identify my strengths and weaknesses in learning languages.)

Intrinsic Motivation for Personal and Academic Growth. This is the second code of the third probed issue. With that, when learners are internally motivated to improve their language competence, they are more likely to persist in their language learning, engage actively in learning activities, and seek out opportunities for language development. Additionally, intrinsic drive not only fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation of the language but also promotes autonomy and self-directed learning, leading to greater proficiency and confidence in language use in various contexts.

Moreover, a participant emphasizes their motivations to achieve their desire for personal and academic growth. Additionally, they want to improve themselves both personally and academically. Hence, learners tend to push to learn the target language particular to enhance competence. Thus, it suggests that they have an internal drive neither the determination to grasp knowledge and skills in the target language, likely to achieve their goals or aspirations. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“So, one of my motivations was first is, it is my desire for personal and academic growth, and also, ginapush po jud na ako akong sarili na magtoon.” (FGD-002)

(One of my motivations is, first and foremost, my desire for personal and academic growth, and also, I am really pushing myself to learn.)

Furthermore, a participant gladly highlights the importance of self-motivation, using it to overcome moments of embarrassment or loss of confidence. Hence, learners maintain a positive outlook, believing that everything can be learned with practice and dedication. The participant acknowledges the need to immerse themselves in learning and actively pursue self-improvement. Overall, their response underscores the significance of self-motivation, positivity, and continuous learning in personal growth. As what Participant 10 stated that:

“Siguro just like what I have said ganiha is Self-motivation. Every time nga ano, basta maulaw ko or mawalaan kong confidence, akong ginaingon lang sa akong self na everything will be okay. Dapat dili ko ma down dayun it is because naay mga butang na di nako kaya. Kay ang tanang butang kay pede sya ma learn so siguro kinahanglan lang nako iimmerse akong self nga I should practice kung naa koy gusto ma learn and self-motivation.” (FGD-010)

(Perhaps, just like what I said earlier, it is self-motivation. Every time I feel embarrassed or lose confidence, I just tell myself that everything will be okay. I shouldn't let myself get down because there are things I can't do. Because everything can be learned, so maybe I just need to immerse myself and practice if there's something I want to learn and self-motivation.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

This study investigated the language learning strategies and language competence among English major students at a local college using a convergent parallel mixed-methods approach. The fifth research question focuses on integrating findings from both the quantitative and qualitative phases. Table 6 presented the results by listing the focal points of the study in the first column. The second and third columns detailed the quantitative findings, which represented the indicators with the highest mean ratings, and the qualitative findings, which provide responses that either confirm or disconfirm the quantitative results. The fourth column explained the nature of how these data sets are integrated, while the fifth column outlines the axiological implications based on the combined data, offering insights into the broader significance of the findings.

Language Learning Strategies. In the quantitative phase, under the indicator of memory, the specific item was rated by the participants as high, thinking in the relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in English. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as enhancement and awareness of language proficiency, specifically in the core idea, awareness on what should be improved within oneself and learn more to widen knowledge in applying the language in every context, under the essential theme of enhancement and awareness of language proficiency. It is safe then to say that the qualitative merges the quantitative.

In the quantitative phase under the cognitive indicator which was rated as high- using English language when presenting a report or augmenting ideas. This result is connected with the qualitative result categorized as interactive learning in diverse contexts specifically in the core idea, applying English language in different situations in academic such as reporting or thesis under the essential theme of enhancement and awareness of language proficiency. It is safe then to say that the qualitative merges the quantitative.

Table 6. *Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings*

<i>Aspect Or Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature Of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Language Learning Strategies of Students	On Table 2 under the indicator memory with an overall mean of 3.93 specifically in item number 1 – thinking in the relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in English (4.15; High).	On table 5 category of enhancement and awareness of language proficiency specifically in core idea 2 - awareness on what should be improved within oneself and learn more to widen my knowledge in applying the language in every context.	Connecting-Merging	The high rating for memory indicates that English major student underscores the crucial role of awareness on what they already know and things that should be improve in language learning.
	On the table 2 under the indicator of cognitive with an overall mean of 4.09 specifically in item number 2 - using English language when presenting a report or augmenting ideas (4.07; High)	On the table 4 under the category of interactive learning in diverse contexts specifically in core idea 2-applying English language in different situations in academic such as reporting or thesis.	Connecting-Merging	The high rating for cognitive indicates that English major students highlight the using the language interactively in diverse contexts in learning the English language
	On the table 2 under the indicator of compensation with an overall mean of 4.13 specifically in the item number 4- attempting to anticipate the person’s upcoming words in English when expressing (3.97; High)	On the table 4 under the category of consistent practice and immersion specifically in core idea 1- having conversation and immersion in using English interactively to practice speaking skills.	Connecting-Merging	The high rating for compensation indicates that English major students emphasize the consistent practice through immersion to enhance their language competence.
	On the table 2 under the indicator of metacognitive with an overall mean of 4.33 specifically in the item number 5- having a clear goal for improving my English skills (4.40; Very High)	On the table 5 under the category of embracing mistakes and challenges for personal growth specifically in the core idea 1- embracing mistakes could help oneself in improvements	Connecting-Merging	The very high rating for metacognitive indicates the English major students underscores their goals to improve their language competence.
	On the table 2 under the indicator of affective with an overall mean of 3.99 specifically in the item number 2- encouraging myself to speak English even when I am afraid of making a mistake (4.30; Very High)	On the table 4 under the category of consistent practice and immersion specifically in the core idea 3- immersing oneself to speak in English even though not that fluent.	Connecting-Merging	The high rating for affective indicates the English major students highlighting the consistent immersion through practice to become better and enhance their language competence
	On the table 2 under the indicator social with an overall mean of 4.05 specifically in the item number 5- asking questions from English with my friends and teachers to help me filled with idea related to the subject (4.0; High).	On the table 4 under the category of seeking guidance and assistance specifically in the core idea 1-consulting with friends and teachers, to help understand better and make decisions.	Connecting-Merging	The high rating for social indicates that English major students emphasize the importance of external factors in seeking guidance and assistance in their language learning.
Language Competence of the Students	On the table 2.1 under the indicator reading with an overall mean of 3.85 high specifically in the item number 4- comprehending the main details of a passage in English materials I read (3.88; High) and item number 5- reading and understanding academic texts in English (4.12; High).	On the table 4 under the category of reading a variety of texts specifically in the core idea 1- practicing oneself in reading as a habit to become efficient and effective speaker of the language.	Connecting-Merging	The high rating for reading indicates that English major students utilize reading materials to practice and enhance their language competence.
	On the table 2.1 under the indicator writing with an overall mean 3.76 specifically in the	On the table 5 under the category of improving language competence specifically in the	Connecting-Merging	The high rating for writing indicates the English major students that they recognize

	<p>item number 1-writing grammatically correct sentences in English (3.71; High).</p> <p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator speaking with an overall mean of 3.59 specifically in the item number 1- speaking English fluently and confidently (3.56; High).</p> <p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator listening with an overall mean of 3.84 specifically in the item number 1- following English conversations and lectures without difficulty (3.69; High).</p> <p>On the table 2 under the indicator comprehension with an overall mean of 4.03 specifically in the item number 2- inferring and interpreting meaning from English texts (3.99; High).</p>	<p>core idea 2-language learning strategies fosters a strong foundation in the aspect of enhancing one’s ability to construct grammatically correct and well-structured sentences, facilitating effective communication.</p> <p>On the table 4 under the category of integration into daily life specifically in the core idea 1- making it a habit to practice more and become efficient and effective speaker of the certain language.</p> <p>On the table 4 under the category of resource limitations to align learning styles specifically in the core idea 2- challenges when it terms to learning the language due to the limited resources that caters the auditory style of learning.</p> <p>On the table 4 under the category of grappling with unfamiliar words specifically in the core idea 1- the hardest challenge in learning English is when encountering unusual words that needed to be learned.</p>	<p>the crucial role of language learning strategies to become better in constructing grammatically correct sentences.</p> <p>The high rating for speaking indicates that English major students highlight the confidence as a part of their practice to become efficient and effective in speaking to enhance their language competence.</p> <p>The high rating for listening indicates the diverging result to English major students in which it contrasts to their various learning styles in developing their language competence.</p> <p>The high rating for comprehension indicates the English major students the inferring and interpreting meaning from English texts to cope their difficulties when grappling unfamiliar words.</p>	
Experiences and Coping Of English Major Students	<p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator speaking specifically in the item number 5- participating effectively in English discussions and conversations with a mean of (3.69; High).</p>	<p>On the table 4 under the essential theme of immersion and active engagement to practice communication skills.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>The high rating of item number 5 in speaking signifies that English major students usually immerse themselves in engagement to practice and enhance their communication skills.</p>
	<p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator comprehension specifically in the item number 4- using dictionaries and other reference materials to comprehend unfamiliar words in English with a mean of (4.19; High)</p>	<p>On the table 4 under the essential theme of deliberate use of various forms of media.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>The high rating of item number 4 in comprehension indicates that English major students usually utilize various forms of resources and materials to cope with unfamiliarity of words.</p>
	<p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator of reading specifically in the item number 3- comprehending the nuances and figurative language in English texts when reading with a mean of (3.73; High).</p>	<p>On the table 4 under the essential theme of navigating difficulties on the complexity of vocabulary.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>The high rating of number 3 in reading indicates the English major students in the navigating difficulties and complexities to comprehend nuances and figurative languages when reading.</p>
	<p>On the table 2 under the indicator of affective specifically in the item number 3- giving myself a reward or treat, when I do well in English with a mean of (3.76; High).</p>	<p>On the table 4 under the essential theme of dynamic process of adaptation and resilience in language learning.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>The high rating of number 3 in affective indicates the English major students giving conditions to produce resilience to achieve success in language learning.</p>
	<p>On the table 2 under the indicator of social specifically in the item number 4- trying to learn about</p>	<p>On the table 4 under the essential theme of proactive approaches in leveraging various resources.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>The high rating of item number 4 in social indicates the English major students highlighting the proactive</p>

	<p>the culture of English speakers with a mean of (3.88; High)</p> <p>On the table 2 under the indicator of affective specifically in the item number 2- asking English speakers to correct me if I am wrong with a mean of (4.21; High).</p>	<p>On the table 4 under the essential theme of fostering positive attitude amidst challenges in language learning.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>approaches to learn the language.</p> <p>The high rating of item number 2 in affective indicates the English major student’s optimism against feedback from the other social factors in return to their language learning</p>
<p>Insights of English Major Students</p>	<p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator of reading specifically in the item number 1-reading English text with no difficulties with a mean of (3.78; High) and speaking specifically in the item number 1- speaking English fluently and confidently with a mean of (3.56; High).</p>	<p>On the table 5 under the essential theme of benefits of language learning strategies.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>In both items number 1 under the reading and speaking indicates the English major students gradually benefits to enhance their competence from language learning strategies.</p>
	<p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator of speaking specifically in the item number 2- expressing my ideas and opinions clearly in English with a mean of (3.59; High) and indicator writing specifically in the item number 4- expressing my ideas and thoughts clearly in written English with a mean of (3.85; High).</p>	<p>On the table 5 under the essential theme of vital role of language learning in communication</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>In both items number 2 and 4 under the speaking and writing indicates the English major students gradually fostered their communications skills as they utilize language learning strategies.</p>
	<p>On the table 2.1 under the indicator of comprehension specifically in the item number 1- understanding English language materials related to my academic field with a mean of (4.09; High) and indicator listening specifically in the item number 1- following English conversations and lectures without difficulty with a mean of (3.69; High).</p>	<p>On the table 5 under the essential theme of impact of LLS on language proficiency and development.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>In both items number 1 under the comprehension and listening indicates the English major students which emphasizes the impact of LLS on developing their language competence</p>
	<p>On the table 2 under the indicator of social specifically in the item number 3- practicing English with other students with a mean of (3.98; High)</p>	<p>On the table 5 under the essential theme of influence of external factors on language learning and competence.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>In the item number 3 particularly under in social it indicates the English major students the significant impact of external factors to learn and enhance competence.</p>
	<p>On the table 2 under the indicator of affective specifically in the item number 3- giving myself a reward or treat, when I do well in English with a mean of (3.76; High) and item number 5- trying to avoid procrastination and nervous, when I am studying or using English in contexts with a mean of (3.85; High).</p>	<p>On the table 5 under the essential theme of personal growth and development in English language through resilience and self-directed learning.</p>	<p>Connecting-Merging</p>	<p>In both items number 3 and 5 under the affective indicates the English major student’s resiliency in learning to foster development in their language competence.</p>

Moreover, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of compensation, it was rated as high by the participants, attempting to anticipate the person’s upcoming words in English when expressing. The result is connected with the qualitative phase which categorized as consistent practice and immersion specifically in the core idea, having conversation and immersion in using English interactively to practice speaking skills under the essential theme of immersion and active engagement to practice communication skills. Thus, this can be viewed that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

Furthermore, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of metacognitive which was rated as very high, having a clear goal for improving my English skills. The result is connected with the qualitative findings which is categorized as, embracing mistakes and challenges for personal growth specifically in the core idea, embracing mistakes could help oneself in improvements under the essential theme of personal growth and development in English language through resilience and self-directed learning. This can be viewed that both quantitative and qualitative merge.

Additionally, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of affective, which was rated as very high by the participants, encouraging myself to speak English even when I am afraid of making a mistake. The result is connected with the qualitative phase which is categorized as, consistent practice and immersion specifically in the core idea immersing oneself to speak in English even though not that fluent under the essential theme of immersion and active engagement to practice communication skills. This can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Consequently, in the quantitative phase under the indicator social, which was rated as high, asking questions from English with my friends and teachers to help me filled with idea related to the subject. The result is connected with the qualitative phase which is categorized as, seeking guidance and assistance specifically in the core idea, consulting with friends and teachers, to help understand better and make decisions under the essential theme of proactive approaches in leveraging various resources. Therefore, it is evident that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

Language Competence. In the quantitative phase, under the indicator of reading which is rated as high, comprehending the main details of a passage in English materials I read and reading and understanding academic texts in English. The result is connected with the qualitative phase which is categorized as reading a variety of texts in the cored idea, practicing oneself in reading as a habit to become efficient and effective speaker of the language under the essential theme of deliberate use of various forms of media. Hence, this can be stated that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

Similarly, in the quantitative phase, under the writing indicator which is rated as high, writing grammatically correct sentences in English. This resulted is connected with the qualitative phase which is categorized as improving language competence specifically in the core idea, language learning strategies fosters a strong foundation in the aspect of enhancing one's ability to construct grammatically correct and well-structured sentences, facilitating effective communication under the essential theme of benefits of language learning strategies. This can be viewed that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase, under the speaking indicator, which was rated as high by the participants, speaking English fluently and confidently. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the category of integration into daily life specifically in the core idea, making it a habit to practice more and become efficient and effective speaker of the certain language under the essential theme of immersion and active engagement to practice communication skills. This can be stated that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

Furthermore, in the quantitative phase, under the listening indicator with a high rating, following English conversations and lectures without difficulty. The result is difference from the qualitative phase under the category of resource limitations to align learning styles specifically in the core idea, challenges when it terms to learning the language due to the limited resources that caters the auditory style of learning under the essential theme of dynamic process of adaptation and resilience in language learning. Thus, the quantitative and qualitative did not meet hence, it is diverging.

Consequently, in the quantitative phase comprehension, which is rated as high, inferring and interpreting meaning from English texts. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the category of grappling with unfamiliar words specifically in the core idea, the hardest challenge in learning English is when encountering unusual words that needed to be learned under the essential theme of navigating difficulties on the complexity of vocabulary. Hence, this can be viewed that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

Experiences and Coping Mechanisms of English Major Students. In the quantitative phase under the indicator speaking, which is rated as high, participating effectively in English discussions and conversations. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme of immersion and active engagement to practice communication skills. Hence, quantitative and qualitative merge.

Similarly, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of comprehension, which is rated as high, using dictionaries and other reference materials to comprehend unfamiliar words in English. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme of deliberate use of various forms of media. Thus, it can be inferred that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of reading which has a high rating, comprehending the nuances and figurative language in English texts when reading. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme of navigating difficulties on the complexity of vocabulary. Hence, it can be inferred that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Furthermore, in the quantitative phase under the affective indicator which has a high rating, giving myself a reward or treat, when I do well in English. The result is connected in the qualitative phase under the essential theme of dynamic process of adaptation and resilience in language learning. Hence, this can be viewed that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

In addition, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of social which has a high rating, trying to learn about the culture of English

speakers and asking English speakers to correct me if I am wrong. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme of proactive approaches in leveraging various resources. Hence, it can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Consequently, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of affective which rated as high, asking English speakers to correct me if I am wrong. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme of fostering positive attitude amidst challenges in language learning. Thus, this can be stated that the quantitative and qualitative merge.

Insights of English Major Students. In the quantitative phase under the indicator of reading and speaking which have a rating of high, reading English text with no difficulties and speaking English fluently and confidently. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme of benefits language learning strategies. This can be concluded that quantitative and qualitative merges.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of speaking and writing which they are rated as high, expressing my ideas and opinions clearly in English and expressing my ideas and thoughts clearly in written English. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme of vital role of language learning in communication. Therefore, it can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Furthermore, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of comprehension and listening which have a high rating, following English conversations and lectures without difficulty understanding English language materials related to my academic field. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme impact of LLS on language proficiency and development. Thus, it can be inferred that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Similarly, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of social which has a high rating, practicing English with other students. The result is connected with the quantitative phase under the essential theme of external factors on language learning and competence. Hence, this can be inferred that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Consequently, in the quantitative phase under the indicator of affective which has a high rating, giving myself a reward or treat, when I do well in English and avoid procrastination and nervous, when I am studying or using English in contexts. The result is connected with the qualitative phase under the essential theme personal growth and development in English language through resilience and self-directed. Hence, this can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative merge.

Status of Language Learning Strategies and Language Competence Among English Major Students

The interpretation of the quantitative data generated from the survey is discussed here. Scholarly works and findings are utilized and cited to support the results of the study. This is done in order to have a robust analysis of the data.

Language Learning Strategies

Presented in the chapter 3 is the status of language learning strategies, which obtained a high level based on the results conducted from the respondents. This means that English major students oftentimes manifested their strategies in their language learning across all year levels. This highlights the students' variety of strategies, which emphasizes the integration of memory, cognitive, metacognitive, compensation, affective, and social strategies in learning a language. They create a supportive practices and environment that reinforces their language learning crucial to help deepen their overall competence in English language.

Moreover, findings were congruence to the study of Habók & Magyar (2018), that students who utilize language learning strategies, stand a better possibility of improving their language competence. It has been stated that, students who are more skilled, use a greater variety of techniques and choose their learning strategies based on the learning tasks. With that, students who understand the value of language learning and employ a variety of techniques may discover fresh possibilities to apply their language skills and advance their knowledge in the target language.

Moreover, in order to master a target language, students must be able to develop their own language learning techniques according to the study of Chanderan & Hashim (2022). Students who are sensitive to utilize their preferred language learning strategies can gain knowledge in learning the English language with convenience and also honing their abilities effectively. Thus, employing such strategies empowers learners to navigate the complexities of language learning with greater efficiency and confidence in every type of contexts.

The first indicator under this variable is memory which obtained a high level. This means that English major students oftentimes manifested their memory strategies in language learning. This implies that students who utilize memory as a learning strategy in the target language, has a greater retention to remember inputs being learned. This approach is crucial for students, as it emphasizes meaningful connections through their existing knowledge and new information of the target language. Also, with consistent use of the target language as well as associating it with various means in every context, learners could strengthen their memory which stand a possibility to retain inputs and effective language learning.

This is in congruence with the study of Balini and Jeyabalan (2018). The study explored how memory strategies help English learners develop their skills to retain information or vocabulary for communication processes. With that, when learners utilize memory strategy, it assists them to recall vocabularies and information in the target language effectively. Hence, it is apparent that memory strategy

training plays a significant role in language learning. The results proved that memory strategy training, has positively contributed to the acquisition of new information/ vocabulary, retention and production as the learners were able to learn the language more easily, effectively and in a self-directed way.

The findings supported also with the study of Flor and Magriz (2018). According to their explanation, a key feature of memory strategies is that they can be consciously controlled and applied based on the learner's intentions. These strategies can be used both to learn a language and to retrieve information from long-term memory, and they are influenced by various factors. Furthermore, the study found that learners preferred using keywords linked to global issues or events, placing these terms in new contexts, employing imagery, and representing sounds to aid in information retrieval.

The second indicator under this variable is cognitive which obtained a high level. This means that English major students oftentimes manifested their cognitive strategies in language learning. This implies that students who use cognitive strategies, significantly improves their understanding and enhanced retention of new information. Additionally, this strategy is an immersive process, through the use of English language in non-academic and academic setting. This strategy not only deepens their language learning but also promotes understanding of the language which they enhance through the means of consistent exposure and application in internalizing English language knowledge.

Aligned with the findings from the study of Wirahyuni and Martha (2022), revealed that students who utilize cognitive strategy were guided to take specific actions, such as clarifying, verifying, guessing, doing inductive and deductive reasoning, practicing, memorizing, and monitoring. Additionally, this enables students to understand and produce language as well as recognize information from different contexts and resources of the target language. They are also required to analyze and created structure for output and input from the target language as it helps students to increase their critical thinking, since students can practice their cognition to make understanding from what they had mastered.

Similarly, with the study of Mashrabovna and Alieva (2023), findings revealed that cognitive factor play a crucial role for learners in the language learning process. These factors help learners in their major intellectual activities such as thinking, reasoning, understanding and as well as problem-solving. Cognitive learning is an efficient learning as they completely engage the learners to increase competency. The study suggested that language teachers and students must be aware of these characteristics and work together to establish an environment that supports effective language learning and cognitive engagement.

This third indicator under this variable is compensation which obtained a high level. This means that English major students oftentimes manifested compensation strategies in their language learning. This strategy implies that students overcome can difficulties in their vocabulary knowledge and enhance their competence since, students are actively engaged in problem solving techniques in navigating language barriers in their learning. Additionally, this flexible strategy allows students to enhance their ability to address challenges in many language contexts when encountering unfamiliar terms hence, they can cope effectively in learning the target language.

In line with the study of Pasumbo and Macora (2020), highlighted the use of compensation strategies since, it can help the students to overcome a lack of appropriate vocabulary. For instance, if learners encounter unfamiliar words in a text, they use the surrounding sentences and the context of the text to guess the meaning. The study revealed that learners use compensation strategies for comprehending the target language in a text when they have insufficient vocabulary or knowledge of the target language. Therefore, through compensation strategy students could maintain interest, motivation and increase their understanding in reading descriptive texts.

Furthermore, the findings also strengthen with the study of Farrokh (2019) which investigated the effect of compensation strategies of Iranian upper-intermediate EFL learners' vocabulary development. The findings revealed that compensation strategies had a positive effect on the participants' vocabulary development. This strategy fosters guessing and using context clues from the unknown and unfamiliar vocabulary. Further, compensation strategies can be applied to help learners to overcome with words that they cannot understand within a text or passage. Hence, when there are unfamiliar words might Iranian students encounter, they tend to utilize compensation tactics since, they also become aware of those vocabularies that limits their understanding within a text, which also helps them in overcoming their constraints.

The fourth indicator under this variable is metacognitive which obtained a very high level. This means that English major students are always manifested metacognitive strategies in language learning. This implies that when English major students are effectively using metacognitive strategies, it fosters a self-regulation and to monitor their progress. Through metacognitive strategies, students have the awareness about the areas they needed to be improve and also, know how to find their strengths from the target language as well as the weaknesses to be addressed hence, they can create a sense of goal in enhancing their language competence.

In connection with the present findings, it strengthens the argument made by Rivas et al. (2022). The findings revealed that metacognition fosters language learners' awareness about their learning progress, in which they can be able to reflect on what they have accomplished and decide how they need to make improvements for a successful learning. Additionally, metacognition involves skills by which learners required the use of mental skills such as planning, monitoring and evaluation. The study recommended the use reflective questions, decision diagrams, and interactive dialogues. This process promotes both metacognitive and critical thinking abilities for successful learning outcomes.

In addition, a study of Okmawati (2020), revealed that when learners use metacognitive strategies, it provides them the awareness that is crucial for them to observe and evaluate their learning processes. The researcher also emphasized that metacognitive skills are essential for helping students identify their weaknesses and areas for improvement in their language competence. These skills enable learners to manage not only their thoughts but also their actions more effectively. Furthermore, when learners successfully apply metacognitive strategies during the learning process, it boosts their confidence and encourages them to become more critical and self-sufficient as ESL or EFL students.

The fifth indicator under this variable is affective which obtained a high level. This means that English major students oftentimes manifested affective strategies in their language learning. It also implies that, when English major students are effectively using affective strategies, it enables them to cope with their fears by maintaining motivation, reduce their level of anxiety and build confidence which leads to an effective and enjoyable language learning. With that, it reinforces learners to have a positive environment for language learning helping to reduce affective filters that hinders their development of their language competence.

This finding supported by the study of Tedjatmaja and Roboh (2017), revealed that affective strategies of the students mainly possess their beliefs, motivation, attitudes and positive emotions that has crucial role in terms of successful language learning. The study also found that, affective strategies are beneficial for struggling students in language learning since, this fosters and provides them a positive outlook in language learning, which is also crucial for them to avoid factors that hinders their learning processes.

Similarly, the findings also supported from the study of Sison (2022), it highlights the affective strategies in lowering the negative factors when teaching and learning English in second language. It revealed that with the use of affective strategies, learners can lower their anxiety, also it fosters encouragement within oneself to use the language when learning as ESL. Moreover, the study used a descriptive comparative in determining the extent of affective strategy. It was found out that the females mostly use affective strategy to lower their anxiety and take emotional temperature especially in encouraging oneself than males.

Lastly, the sixth indicator under this variable is social which obtained a high level. This means that English major students oftentimes manifested social strategies in their language learning. This implies that, English major students use social strategies to come up with a language knowledge that they can learn with other people through interactive processes, directing them to further enhance their language abilities. With that, this offers learners with collaboration among others which it creates a sense of engagement and build understanding with each other to help enhance competence in their language learning in a positive and supportive environment.

In congruence with the study of Mandasari et al. (2018) which revealed that social strategy is one of the effective techniques in language learning primarily in developing the student's speaking skills. This strategy fosters collaboration among the students in practicing a dialogue which helps in developing their speaking skills of the target language. Additionally, many students have lack of confidence when using the target language in specific contexts hence, collaborating with friends at the same age level can help boost in language learning, especially on their speaking ability. This opportunity provides students to actively engage in language learning without worrying about grammar or sentence structure mistakes.

Furthermore, this strengthened by the study of Faqih et al. (2023) which revealed that in order to support English language learners in practicing their language skills effectively, particularly in engaging conversations using the target language with their peers felt more comfortable. It is also important for learners to have learning environments that often offer support and encouragement and shared progress. With that, it is crucial to educate them about the significance of social strategies to help them engage as it fosters to improve their English language learning. Additionally, the study established the correlation between the use of social strategies which fosters a deeper understanding of the languages' nuances and cultural context as a tool also helping to enhance language competence and motivation among the learners.

Language Competence

As shown, the second variable of this study is language competence, which obtained a high level based on the results conducted from the respondents. This means that English major students oftentimes manifested their language competence in the target language. This highlights that students have developed a well-rounded competency across all language skills, encompassing the reading, writing, speaking, listening and comprehension. This means also that, students recognized these abilities' significance in equipping their language ability, evident for effective engagement in varied language learning opportunities and academic success.

The findings are congruence with the study presented by Siami and Chuaungo (2021). The results revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between language competence and academic performance. It was also found that, a students' academic success is enhanced when students are competent in their target language, also it supports them to adapt without difficulties in different learning environment. Therefore, through enhancing their ability to understand and engage with course materials, participate in discussions, and effectively communicate ideas is crucial to their academic success. By having strong language skills also contribute to better performance in assessments and increased confidence social interactions.

Moreover, it is connected also with the study presented by Izzatulah et al. (2022) which revealed that language competency is an important indicator for better academic achievement of students, where the English is second language. Further, language competence can be viewed the ability of a student to read, write, listen, comprehend and respond using the language in various contexts. Further,

the results found also, that there is a significant positive relationship between language proficiency and academic performance. The more the student mastered the various skills using the English language, the better he/she will be able to perform academically.

The first indicator under this variable is reading which obtained a high level. This means that reading is regarded by the English major students as oftentimes manifested. This implies that reading is significant for students in their language competence, since it is a key component to excel in their academic pursuits. In this ability, students could expose themselves into diverse language structures with complex definitions since, it improves their comprehension to interpret and analyze various literary texts. With that, reading makes learners develop their ability to gain excessive knowledge and understanding with the text decoded in English language, aimed to enhance their language competence.

This connects to the study presented by Grell (2022), findings revealed that the goal of reading is to help learners understand and grasp information in written texts as it requires an active process in the context of language learning. For instance, when students were having difficulties to read, they struggle in accessing and comprehending written information which impedes their learning and academic performance. Moreover, the study highlighted that reading is an active process involving both simple and complex elements. It emphasized that readers need a foundational knowledge of the language, including vocabulary and a general understanding of the grammar rules specific to that language.

It was added by the study of Wani and Ismail (2024) highlighted that a lack of reading habits is often linked to poorer performance in English among students, underscoring the need to cultivate this skill. The study found that reading is a crucial component for significantly enhancing students' knowledge acquisition, vocabulary development, and critical thinking abilities. Additionally, it recommended making reading a mandatory activity at all educational levels, suggesting that students should be provided with at least one text to read each week. Furthermore, it proposed monitoring students' reading progress through reading diaries that track various registers or vocabulary encountered, along with summaries of the books read.

The second indicator under this variable is writing which obtained a high level. This means that writing is regarded by the English major students as oftentimes manifested. This implies that writing skill is also crucial for students in their language competence since, it encompasses the students' ability to reinforce their use of appropriate grammar and vocabulary focusing on both accuracy and creativity in writing academic text essential for academic success. This also highlights, to keep students write down their thoughts with clarity, fostering a sense of effective communication.

This is in congruence with the study presented by Canisi and Lambencio (2023). The results of the study found that, most of the writing convention errors committed by the students were in grammar, diction and incorrect use of punctuation marks was the least made error. It was added with the findings that, students had a fair competency level in writing essays therefore, most of the students agreed that writing is an important skill in English. It is an essential skill that allows them to provide effective communication through written form, enabling to create clear expression of ideas and critical thinking that involves the representation of a language with symbols.

Also, another study made by Zeng (2018) strengthened the findings which explored the efficient ways to integrate writing into the whole process of English language learning. The study found that writing is not only one of the four basic language skills in English language learning, but also a crucial means of exchanging ideas in social interactions in written form. It is commonly regarded as a reflection of ones' language competence and overall quality. The study highlights the significance of writing beyond its basic function, emphasizing its role in personal and professional communication. Also, it paves an importance of developing writing skills in English learners for better communication and social integration.

The third indicator under this variable is speaking which obtained a high level. This means that speaking is regarded by the English major students as oftentimes manifested. This implies that English major students, viewed speaking as crucial for their language competence as it enables students to have a real-time practice of their pronunciation, fluency, and interactive communication skills, which are significant component of their speaking ability for effective language use in varied contexts. This ability not only enhances their strong communication in participating discussions but also prepares them for diverse social interaction.

This finds support to the study of Maba (2022). The study examined students' speaking competence to gain a clearer understanding of their abilities, revealing that most had sufficient skills to articulate their thoughts and actively engage in discussions. However, the study also identified gaps in certain areas particular in the use of correct grammar and language functions, where some students struggled to express their ideas with clarity and accuracy. This suggests that while students may have the foundational ability to engage in conversations, there is still a need for targeted instructional support to enhance their linguistic precision and fluency. This approach strengthens the students' ability to communicate effectively and also equip them with the skills necessary to engage in diverse communicative scenarios, both academically and real-world situations.

Similarly, the findings parallel to the study of Rao (2019) which emphasized, that effective speaking skills are deemed the most crucial among the four language skills for successful communication in globalized world particularly focusing on the speaking skills for English language learners (ELLs). Additionally, it argues that effective speaking skill is essential for achieving communication, academic and professional success as a central component. The study suggested that, English classrooms are the ideal setting for developing these speaking skills and stresses the need for teachers to adapt their methods and materials to better support ELLs. Lastly, it highlights the value of incorporating group and pair activities to enhance speaking competency and outlines various techniques and

strategies for teachers to improve students' speaking abilities.

The fourth indicator under this variable is listening which obtained a high level. This result is indicative that speaking is regarded by the respondents as oftentimes manifested. This implies that listening is crucial for students in their language competence since, it allows them to follow conversations and lectures without having difficulties also, gradually improves their ability to identify specific details and ideas highlighting their focus and comprehension during their listening tasks. With that, this listening ability prepare students to engage effectively in English language medium, from academic setting to everyday interactions.

It was added by the study of Vani and Naik (2023). The study emphasized that, apprehending information relies to an individuals' ability to listen hence, it plays a crucial role in effective communication. The study found that learners develop strong communication skills when they possess good listening abilities. Additionally, it was noted that practicing listening skills through activities like listening to music, watching English movies, and attending English language courses enhances their ability to focus on detailed information. Therefore, the study emphasizes the effectiveness of Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) in improving students' listening skills, as good listening abilities contribute to better communication development.

This relates also with the study made by Lopez et al., (2020), it was found that active listening is crucial in learning a language hence, active listening is required to the target language to improve language competence over the time. Furthermore, it serves as an important means of language learning, aimed at helping students acquire information generated from a target language. The findings also indicated that active listening is crucial in the language learning and acquisition process, positively affecting various aspects of learning. It has a significant impact on phonology, morphology, and pragmatics. Therefore, it is recommended that learners prioritize active listening as a key strategy for enhancing their language learning.

Lastly, the fifth indicator under this variable is comprehension which obtained a high level. This result is indicative that comprehension is regarded by the respondents as oftentimes manifested. This implies that students have developed strong comprehension skills in English particularly, within their academic field as it allows them to understand texts that contains idioms and figurative languages accurately through a various form of English language materials. This ability to infer and interpret meaning from texts reflects a deep engagement with the various language materials hence, this skill equips students to navigate complex academic content with confidence.

This is in congruence with the study presented by Rodge et. At. (2019), which emphasized that students who begin school with competence in a certain language are more likely to develop adequate comprehension abilities and achieve academic success of the target language, than students who struggle with poor language competence in their early years. Moreover, the result of the study stated that comprehension has the potential to increase students' general language competences since, learners' ability to comprehend new information is a critical concept in language learning as one that can determine the learners' capacity to absorbed language elements and use them in a varied context.

Also, the findings parallel to the study of Martinez (2020) which emphasized that, language comprehension plays a crucial role among English learners (ELs) in understanding and supporting their literacy achievement. Focusing on the language comprehension domain can be a highly effective strategy to assist the expanding group of learners supporting to develop their literacy skills, necessary to access the curriculum meaningfully. The study also emphasized that, developing language comprehension, educators can provide ELs with the tools they need to succeed academically and engage more deeply with the learning process.

Lived Experiences and Coping Mechanisms of English Major Students on their Language Learning Strategies and Language Competence

The lived experiences and Coping Mechanisms of English students with regards to the effectiveness of language learning strategies in their language competence was shown in the previous chapter. Notably, different issues were probed which provoked various core ideas which were grouped into categories. This aimed to have a better understanding on the experiences of the English major education students in using various language learning strategies and how it benefits to enhance their language competence. With this, different propositions from the different authors and theorists were presented relative to these experiences.

Immersion and Active Engagements to Practice Communication Skills. The findings of the study revealed from the experiences of English major students in their language learning to help enhance their current competence in English language. Recognizing that through immersion and active engagement, they can gain additional knowledge from various contexts better to grasp and enhance learners in language development further enhancing communication skills. This result finds support in Input Hypothesis, proposed by Stephen Krashen (1974). According to the concept of input hypothesis, learners acquire language when they encounter comprehensible input in real-life contexts that is slight beyond their competence which promotes natural- acquisition helping to reinforce and internalize new language structures. This theory highlights the importance of providing learners with language input that is both understandable and slightly challenging to support natural language development and acquisition.

Moreover, the present finding strengthens the argument made by Shawaqfeh et al., (2023) emphasized students that, through immersion and active engagement are crucial factor that influences their learning of English language. This essential component of learning English language was determined that interaction continues to be a fundamental strategy, which regularly used to improve their learning

in English language particular in the academic and social contexts. The study also found that, when students immersed in active engagements it encourages learners in open communication exposure, which speeds up their acquisition and learning of language abilities in a short amount of time.

Similarly, this solidifies the finding made by Yulia et al., (2023). The study examined students that are immersed to social interaction as an alternative approach to improve their communication skills using English. The results found that active engagement particular with their classmates and friends became a factor in enhancing their English language proficiency. The interesting findings informed that, immersing oneself on social engagement is important when combined with vocabulary to improve English competency resulting to better refine and improved communication skill.

Deliberate use of Various Forms of Media. The findings of the study revealed from the experiences of English major students that, they utilized various materials and media that contains texts related to the target language as their strategy also, seeking to widen their vocabulary and enhance their language competence in all aspect. Hence, using various forms of media could offer them in diverse linguistic contexts that significantly enhances their comprehension and language skills. The result finds support with Media Ecology Theory, proposed by Neil Postman (1971). According to the theory, this examines how media and communication technologies influences human perception, knowledge, behavior and culture. Postman emphasizes that media are not just tools for communication but also environments that are shaped by human interactions. Thus, it emphasizes the rise of digital media has transformed on how people communicate, access information, and engage with each other.

Further, the findings strengthen along with the study of Rubio and Conesa (2022), which the study focused on the integration of various digital tool in learning English language for the students. The study found a displayed positive impact regarding the use of digital tools in learning the target language. Moreover, it was found that the varied digital tools are crucial for honing specific language skills or content of the students, which helps them to encounter diverse vocabulary and comprehension when it terms to language usage in various contexts. Therefore, digital tools and their impact in the context of English learning benefits students and provides more advantages. Additionally, incorporating media that aligns with learners' interests fosters an increase of motivation and make the learning process effective.

Moreover, the findings agreed also with the study of Strom and Frojd (2021), which investigated to what extent students in the primary years incorporate digital tools in their language learning practice, and more specifically, how this significantly contributes or impact the student's vocabulary acquisition and learning the target language. The results implied that a variation of tasks and digital tools, as well as a frequency in exposure of content, is necessary for beneficial vocabulary acquisition/learning. Thus, the use of varied digital tools and frequent exposure to content significantly enhances primary students' vocabulary acquisition and overall learning of the target language.

Navigating Difficulties on the Complexity of Vocabulary. The findings of the study revealed that, English major students experienced difficulties in language learning such as encountering unfamiliar words and phrases, however delving through this difficulty may foster deeper understanding in language, enabling students to enhance their language competence. The findings aligned with the Input Hypothesis of Stephen Krashen (1974). According to the theory, this conceptualizes that when learners navigate to difficulties with complexity of vocabularies, learners acquire new vocabulary most effectively when they are exposed to input that is slightly beyond their current competency level. With that, Krashen emphasized that learners should be introduced to complex vocabulary, allowing them to make connections and infer meanings. Thus, the theory highlights that increasing the complexity of the vocabulary input, learners can build their language skills in a manageable and progressive manner.

Further, the findings are further supported by the study of Rosyada and Apoko (2023), which investigated the challenges students face in their vocabulary learning process and the strategies they use to overcome them. The study revealed that many students struggled with issues such as correctly pronouncing new words, accurate spelling, proper usage of word meanings, and effective vocabulary retention. It also showed that students addressed these challenges by employing strategies such as using media resources, taking notes, and consulting dictionaries, which helped them strengthen their ability to learn the target language independently.

Moreover, findings agreed with the study of Susanto (2021) which examined the factors of students' difficulties in learning vocabulary. The findings showed, that the students faced difficulties in vocabulary learning particularly, in pronouncing the words, correct spelling, different grammatical form and choosing appropriate meaning of the words, leading students' to be confused in using the word based on the context. The study revealed that, students addressed their concerns by utilizing a multi-faced approach on their language learning including their consistent practice in pronunciation, contextual usage exercises, improving their retention and enhanced tools which strengthens their learning when it terms to vocabulary particularly in English language.

Dynamic Process of Adaptation and Resilience in Language Learning. The findings of the study revealed that English major students have their own ways in addressing their problems when it terms to their language learning, also in choosing appropriate learning styles and resources fit to their learning preference better for enhancing their language competence. This finding aligned with Constructivism Theory proposed by Jean Piaget (1896). According to this, theory students actively construct their understanding through experiences and interactions with their environment, which continually adapts their mental schemas to accommodate knowledge and skills. Piaget emphasized that, adaptation involves two key processes of assimilation, where learners incorporate new information into existing

cognitive structures, and accommodation, where they modify these structures to accommodate new information. This theory highlights that this approach promotes resilience in learning as they are empowered to construct their own knowledge and solve problems through contexts and personalized experiences.

Moreover, these findings were supported with the study of Triananda (2022) which investigated the learning styles of EFL students. The study revealed that, students have individual preferences that aid their comprehension of learning materials. The findings showed that most students preferred a multimodal learning style, combining read/write and kinesthetic approaches. Read/write learners favored text, reading, and note-taking, while kinesthetic learners learned best through hands-on activities and practical exercises. Therefore, effective teaching strategies for EFL students should incorporate a blend of multimodal learning approaches to cater the diverse learning preferences and enhance comprehension.

Furthermore, the findings agree with the study of Chen (2023). The study examined the impact of learner's learning preference that matches their learning environment and resources. Moreover, each student receives information in a different way therefore, they must utilize their preferred method of learning the language to maximize their potential. The results showed that, learning preferences uniquely affect students' foreign language learning, and students should choose them wisely for better academic performance. When learning preferences aligned with the environment and resources, students can achieve language competence and academic success more easily.

Proactive Approaches in Leveraging Various Resources. Students amidst their difficulties, highlighted the social factors as their approach from reinforcements which has a huge role to make a positive influence towards their learning helping to achieve development in language competence. The findings were supported by Albert Bandura's Concept of Modeling on Social Learning Theory (1977). According to Social Learning Theory, this conceptualizes the proactive use of diverse resources by facilitating learning through observation, imitation, and social interaction as an influence in shaping the learner's learning experiences. Bandura, emphasizes the of role of observational learning and modeling in acquiring new skills by actively seeking diverse resources, learners are exposed to multiple which enhances their understanding and retention. This theory highlights that proactive engagement allows learners to witness different behaviors and strategies that provides opportunities for social interaction and collaboration, crucial for the development of self-efficacy and motivation.

Moreover, it was strengthened by the study of Sefiu (2023), which examined how social factors particular a supportive environment influences English language learning outcomes among elementary students in the municipality of Gjilan. Further, the study emphasizes learning as a social process occurring through interactions, considering the interdependence of social context and personal development. The findings revealed that, having a supportive environment is viewed as an important factor for learners' English language learning, with direct assistance being the most common form. Additionally, the strong connection between a parent's level of education and their child's English performance serves as positive role models, leading to better behavior and academic performance of the students.

Moreover, the findings are supported by the study of Shaddad and Jember (2024), which examined the effects of feedback-supported tasks and peer-work activities on language learners' engagement, self-esteem, and language development at a university in Saudi Arabia. The results demonstrated a significant increase in engagement, self-esteem, and language growth in the experimental group compared to the control group. These findings underscore the value of incorporating collaborative and feedback-oriented approaches into language instruction to enhance students' learning outcomes. The study employed a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design, with 45 participants in the experimental group and 43 in the control group, who underwent 15 sessions. The control group received traditional instruction.

Fostering Positive Attitude Amidst Challenges in Language Learning. The students have shared their coping mechanism towards the challenges in language learning, amidst those hurdles which learners always make their pave in achieving success, by believing from their selves in such of having a positive mindset, which eliminates all the negativities. The findings supported by the Self- Efficacy Theory of Albert Bandura (1977). According to the theory, individuals believe in their own capabilities influencing how people think, feel, and behave. Bandura emphasizes that positive attitude and belief in their ability to succeed helps learners approach challenges with confidence and persistence, crucial for building self-efficacy. This theory highlights maintaining a positive outlook by reinforcing the belief that effort and perseverance lead to improvement and promoting continuous progress in learning.

Moreover, the findings strengthened with the study of Suman (2019). The study focused on fostering positive attitudes toward learning English. The findings indicated that success in acquiring a target language depends not only on intellectual ability but also on the learner's attitude toward language learning. The study concluded that mastering a second language is influenced not only by cognitive competence or language skills but also by the learner's positive attitude toward the target language. As a result, students should maintain a positive outlook and optimism about learning the language to enhance their overall success.

Moreover, this finds support with the study of Zintz (2018) which explored the effectiveness of optimistic mindset as an instrument on student's language learning. The results from the study revealed that, students who persevere in their language learning when faced with challenges seem to have grit, which correlates with a growth mindset. Additionally, the study also highlighted that those who were able to persevere on a difficult task are more likely to have success, than a student who believed that learning is determined by innate ability. The effectiveness of an optimistic mindset in the school culture requires to have supportive strategies as well as expectations

needed support students to be able to implement a growth mindset into academic instruction.

Insights Shared with the English Major Students with Regards to the Effectiveness of Language Learning Strategies in Developing their Language Competence

Benefits of Language Learning Strategies. Students shared their insights on the effectiveness of language learning strategies in developing their linguistic abilities. They utilize various strategies tailored to their preferences to effectively enhance their current competence. The findings supported by the theory of Jean Piaget's Cognitive Theory (1936). According to this theory, learners assimilate new information and accommodate it within their existing cognitive frameworks, supporting the transition to more abstract and complex knowledge. Piaget emphasizes the active role of learners in constructing their understanding, building on existing cognitive structures through developmental stages sensorimotor, pre-operational, concrete operational, and formal operational which represent different levels of cognitive maturity and complexity. This theory highlights the importance of experiences and interactions in shaping cognitive growth, enabling learners to develop higher-order thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Moreover, the findings were supported with the study of Almosalami (2022), which investigated the learning strategies adopted by Saudi university students and explored the differences in the use of learning strategies to their academic achievement. The study revealed that, micro strategies and study habits are the most preferred strategies by Saudi university students. Additionally, the study also found that adopting these strategies, students improved their academic performance and the ability better to retain information as well as consistent study practices. Thus, the study concluded that their diverse language learning strategies benefit university students by enhancing their ability to effectively construct and apply their new language skills which paves way to improve their overall language competence and academic success.

Similarly, the findings strengthen with the study of Digessew and Beriso (2022), which assessed the language learning strategies used by English major students at Addis Ababa University. The study revealed that the strategies, ranked from most to least used, were metacognitive, social, affective, compensation, cognitive, and memory. It also found that language learning strategies play a key role in determining how effectively students learn a second or foreign language. These strategies were identified as essential tools for helping students successfully acquire the desired knowledge and skills, particularly in the English language.

Vital Role of Language Learning in Communication. In this aspect students particular in language learning specifically, who utilized strategies, expressed their claims that it is the solid foundation to develop competence in the target language hence, this paves a path to achieve success in communication. This claim is supported by the Communicative Competence Theory proposed by Dell Hymes (1967). According to Communicative Competence Theory, communication encompasses not only the grammatical correctness of language but also the ability to use language appropriately in various social contexts. Hymes emphasized that knowing a language is not just about mastering its structure, but also about knowing how to use it effectively and appropriately in various communicative situations. This theory highlights the holistic view of language competence goes beyond grammatical accuracy to include the social and functional use of language.

Moreover, the findings were supported with the study of Faris (2022), which aimed to assess the effect of English language learning on the use of effective communication. The results of this study after the dissemination of survey questionnaires, it was concluded that there is a great effect when learning English language on the use of effective communication. Additionally, language learning also promotes students' fluency in speaking, because the students can communicate without any restrictions, also it can be inferred that effective communication aid students to circumvent their language difficulties. Thus, language learning enables the students with high competency level to survive in communication.

Similarly, the findings also find support with the study of Yadav (2024), which the study investigated how the role of language learning contributes to the communicate skills among EFL students and how this affects their willingness to communicate. The findings revealed that, language learning plays a crucial role in communication by facilitating a successful cross-cultural communication across various domains, including interpersonal interactions, academic achievements, and professional opportunities. Hence, the result signifies that student learned the usage of language appropriately according to its context thereby, it is highly valued in the globalization which open the doors for a wide range of professional opportunities and career advancement prospects. Therefore, investing in English language learning is essential for achieving success in cross-cultural communication in this globalized world.

Impact of LLS on Language Proficiency and Development. In this phase participants shared their insights on how language learning strategies significantly contributed various profound improvement on their language competency and development in all aspect. The findings aligned with Constructivism Theory which was proposed by Jean Piaget (1896). According to Constructivism Theory, learners actively construct their understanding and reflective processes through experiences and interactions with their environment. Piaget emphasizes that adaptation involves two key processes of assimilation, where learners incorporate new information into existing cognitive structures, and accommodation, where they modify these structures to accommodate new information and skills. This theory highlighted approaches that promotes resilience in learning as they are empowered to construct their own knowledge and reflective processes to solve problems through contexts.

Furthermore, the findings strengthen the argument made by the study of Arashidi (2022) which highlights both the competency levels and the relationship between students' use of language learning strategies. The study found that students frequently employed these

strategies, demonstrating strong awareness of their learning processes and personal development in acquiring the English language. Additionally, it revealed a positive correlation between proficiency levels and the use of language learning strategies, indicating that students can effectively learn the target language by utilizing these approaches.

Moreover, the findings are supported by the study of Taleb and Kurum (2022), which explored the types of foreign language learning strategies used by high school students and their impact on English learning achievement. The survey included questions about learners' use of strategies in areas such as reading, listening, writing, speaking, translation, and vocabulary knowledge in the target language. The results revealed a strong correlation between students' use of language learning strategies and their success in English. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that increasing English learners' awareness of various strategies may enhance their language competency.

Influence of External Factors on Language Learning and Competence. The students shared their perspective about how external factors contribute success in their language learning helping to enhance their language competence. The finding is aligned with Social Learning Theory proposed by Albert Bandura (1977). According to Social Learning Theory, learners acquire knowledge and skills by observing and imitating proficient speakers, including teachers, peers, and media role models. Bandura emphasizes the role of modeling, where individuals observe others' which influences their cognitive processes, such as attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation in learning. This theory highlights that cultural context and social norms surrounding learners in shaping their understanding, which provide opportunities for practice and feedback.

The findings are also supported by Rafique and Javaid's (2023) study, which highlighted the impact of social factors on students' language learning success and the development of their competence. This study focused on examining Taiwanese children's motivation and attitudes toward learning English, as well as the influence of social factors on their language acquisition. The results provided further insights into how these factors shape English learning in Taiwanese elementary schools. The study found that elementary students exhibited positive learning behaviors, stronger motivation, and a more favorable attitude, along with increased motivation to learn. Additionally, students' academic success was enhanced when parents actively guided them with their homework.

Furthermore, the findings are supported by Khanh Ly's (2024) study, which examined the role of social factors, particularly the role of teachers, in promoting student-centered language learning to improve English competence. The study revealed that English teachers, by taking on various roles such as controllers, assessors, managers, and facilitators, play a key part in creating a dynamic, student-focused learning environment. This approach encourages learner autonomy, motivation, and self-directed learning throughout the language acquisition process. The study concluded that this teacher influence is a crucial factor in students' language learning success, providing more opportunities for language development and academic achievement.

Personal Growth and Development in English Language through Resilience and Self-directed Learning. The students also shared their insights on how they fostered resilience in learning the language through from their desires, which enable them to overcome amidst the challenges and setbacks. In addition, it empowers the learners to take ownership of their language learning process, leading to the success for the desire of improvement on their current competence. The findings aligned with the Self-Determination Theory along with the proponents Edward Deci and Richard Ryan (1985). According to Self-Determination Theory, human motivation is driven by the need to fulfill three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Deci and Ryan emphasize that when individuals' needs are met, they experience enhanced intrinsic motivation, well-being, and personal growth. This theory highlights environment and practices that support human desire and needs can significantly enhance motivation and development of an individual.

Moreover, the findings are supported by the study conducted by Haidar et al. (2019), which aimed to explore the motivations of Pakistani undergraduate students majoring in English in Islamabad, focusing on their reasons for choosing English as their field of study. The results revealed that the students' connection with the English language is not merely for prestige; rather, they have a deeper affinity for it, which includes a desire to adopt a native-like identity, achieve global solidarity, and enhance their communicative competence. Furthermore, the passion for the English language and its literature can positively impact students' motivation to excel in their studies and promote personal growth, even as they navigate challenges. As a result, their enthusiasm for learning English helps maintain their interest and drive to succeed in their chosen major.

Consequently, the findings also supported with the study of Zarrinabadi et al., (2022), which highlighted that learning a second language is a process, where resilience and self-directed learning plays a crucial role in helping learners cope with difficulties. Therefore, the study examined factors influencing resilience and self-directed learning through its effects on 300 Iranian EFL learners. The results showed that, resilience and self-directed learning significantly predicts both engagement in learning and overall well-being, indicating that resilient learners are more engaged and happier. Additionally, growth language mindsets and ideal L2 self were found to predict resilience, which in turn predicted engagement and well-being, suggesting the importance of fostering resilience in language education.

Conclusions

The study's findings led to the following conclusions: First, the use of language learning strategies among English major students is high across various aspects, including memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective, and social strategies. Similarly, their language competence is also high in key areas such as reading, writing, speaking, listening, and comprehension. This indicates that

English major students consistently exhibit strong indicators of both effective language learning strategies and high language competence.

Second, the findings revealed a significant relationship between language learning strategies and language competence among English major students. This conclusion, supported by the Mean, R-Value, and P-Value, shows that both variables are statistically significant. The results indicate a strong correlation between the use of language learning strategies and the level of language competence among the students.

Third, a thematic analysis of the qualitative data, derived from in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD), offered deeper insights into the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of English major students. This analysis highlighted how students utilized language learning strategies to enhance their language competence and revealed various situations that impact their approach to language learning. The qualitative findings provided a richer understanding of the contexts and challenges faced by students in their efforts to improve their language skills. The following themes emerged: Immersion and Active Engagement to Practice Communication Skills, Deliberate Use of Various Forms of Media, Navigating Difficulties on The Complexity of Vocabulary, Dynamic Process of Adaptation and Resilience in Language Learning, Proactive Approaches in Leveraging Various Resources and Fostering Positive Attitude Amidst Challenges in Language Learning.

Fourth, from the participants responses, other themes are identified which show the insights shared of English major students with regards to the effectiveness of language learning strategies on their language competence. The following are the themes: Benefits of Language Learning Strategies, Vital Role of Language Learning in Communication, Impact of LLS on Language Proficiency and Development, Influence of External Factors on Language Learning and Competence and Personal Growth and Development in English Language through Resilience and Self-Directed Learning.

Lastly, to gain a clearer understanding of how language learning strategies affect the language competence of English major students, the responses were thematically analyzed to validate the qualitative results of the study. The integration of findings from both phases, as outlined in the research plan, showed alignment between the quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative results, which assessed the status of language learning strategies (LLS) and language competence (LC) among participants, were consistent with the qualitative findings. Both sets of results confirm that language learning strategies significantly enhance students' language competence across various areas, improving their ability to understand nuances, engage in discourse, and apply linguistic functions in diverse contexts.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Since the status perceived by English major students the language learning strategies, it reveals that among the six indicators, the memory has the lowest mean among of them, which indicates that English major students are unlikely use the strategy in developing their language competence, it is recommend that students must acknowledge the fundamental worth of memorization strategy in fostering language development and learning. The memory strategy should be given priority despite the indicator's present lower mean. This may be achieved by the students to integrate memory strategies into language learning by incorporating mnemonic devices, such as acronyms or visualization techniques, helping students retain vocabulary and grammar rules more effectively. Additionally, implementing spaced repetition techniques can reinforce language concepts over time, enhancing long-term memory retention. Therefore, by incorporating memory as a strategy in language learning, students will likely to retrieve inputs which is far to be forgotten helping to maintain their retention and achieve the competency enhancement.

Additionally, the status perceived by English major students the language competence, it reveals that among the five indicators, the speaking competency has the lowest mean among of them, which indicates that students may find it difficult to develop throughout their learning, it is recommend that practical use of the learnt input must be applied throughout the context of the students in which they deal with. Hence, putting much emphasis on the authentic application, students can find engagements in their specific contexts, dealing with other people to practice their speaking abilities to attain the fluency they desired. Additionally, fluent speaking skills enable students to express themselves articulately and confidently in various contexts, facilitating smoother interactions in preparatory for their professional fields, social situations, and academic environments hence, fosters better relationships and opportunities. Thus, improved speaking fluency enhances comprehension skills, enabling individuals to adapt to different linguistic nuances and effectively navigate diverse communication scenarios.

Moreover, in the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences of English major students with regards to their language learning strategies in pursuit of enhancing their language competence particular in English language, students must find those strategies that is suitable to their learning preferences so that, there is convenience when it comes to learning. With that, understanding the utilization of preferred learning style can enhance student's engagement and motivation which fosters a deeper and more sustainable grasp of information in the target language. Also, regular practice could solidify and enhance one's knowledge about the target language, particular in applying the language to a target situation or certain contexts, since direct experience of students can facilitate deeper understanding and retention of linguistic concepts while enhancing practical communication skills, which foster a good foundation in building relationships. The findings from the qualitative phase essentially imply that students are actively knowing itself that best describes their novel ways to get effective strategies in learning the target language, which could help them to enhance their current

competence.

Further, in the phase of coping mechanism among the English major students with regards to the hindrances seeking to enhance their language competence, this may help students to address their challenges and difficulties that they faced in the process of learning and development. Learning the language may require some extended support, motivation and guidance from the factors whom could help to achieve the success particular in developing the competence of the target language. It is crucial also for a student to possess optimism further to the brighter side, since it reinforces the learners to enthusiastically learn and develop their aspects in language. On the other hand, in the process of learning mistakes is such an opportunity to become wiser and better, as a student refrain to be discouraged and accept these factors since, it contributes to the overall success of the language growth and success. Thus, enabling these attributes will pave way to the students to achieve the success of language learning leading to the desire of developing its competence in all aspect.

Consequently, those shared insights from English major students with regards to the effectiveness of language learning strategies may help them to address their needs in enhancing their language competence. Further, having the perspectives and awareness may help students to refine their set of skills and competences with regards to the language. This might allow learners to make informed decision and tailor their specific needs based from their preferences in order to learn. The students could also underscore the resilience, growth and development as an individual in the society through performing the function of an effective communicator, which results to the foundation of building good relationships with others and success in the various fields. Furthermore, the point of view of embracing mistakes in language learning fosters a growth mindset, encouraging learners to view errors as opportunities for improvement rather than setbacks. By actively engaging with and learning from mistakes, learners develop resilience, confidence, and a deeper understanding of the language. These perceptions could maintain the value of a greater possibilities and a positive environment towards the process of learning resulting to a more productive and success of language learning.

In addition, the researcher wanted to recommend, the integration of the various interactive tools and websites using the technologies that emerges in these present times, unlikely with the traditional form of learning, utilization of these mechanisms paves an easier way to develop the student's language competency and will cater for more diverse learning style and techniques for the learners. Additionally, participate in the various programs particular in language exchange to enrich one's ability to become an effective learner and user of the English language. Also, widen the perspective on the impact of this language in the context of globalization, for this instance this will empower the desire and will to learn the language since, there are various opportunities that awaits, longing for the use of the latent abilities which could contribute to the overall impact of the society.

Lastly, make use of the factors that makes beneficial in the learner's success. With that, having a support system that provides encouragement and motivation, which are crucial for staying committed to language learning, especially during challenging times. Interacting with supportive individuals allows for opportunities to practice language skills in a safe and encouraging environment, boosting confidence and fluency. Furthermore, encourage oneself to accept feedbacks and guidance from the other people to identify areas for improvement such in weaknesses and strengths to refine language competence. Thus, the emotional and social support from others fosters a sense of belonging and accountability, enhancing the overall success of language learning endeavors.

References

- Afdaleni, (2018). Affective Learning Strategies Used to Improve Student's English Reading Comprehension by College Students. *Advances in Social Science, Education Humanities Research (ASSEHR)*.
- Aguelo, R.F. (2017). Enhancing Student's Language Competencies through Collaborative Learning. Assumption College Thonburi.
- Ahmad, M.S. & Javid, S. (2023). The Impact of External Factors on Learner's Learning English and Their Achievement at University Level.
- Alaon, C.L., Santos, J.D. & San Jose, A. (2023). Improving Speaking Communication Skills in English through Self-Directed Strategy. *International Journal of Educational Innovation and Research*. Volume 2 (1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31949/ijeir.v2i1.2920>
- Al-Atabi, A.K., (2020). What is Writing. University of Baghdad. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35570.53440>.
- Alazamil, J. (2021). Listening Skills: Important but Difficult to Learn. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)* Volume 12. doi:<https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol12no3.25>.
- Al-Balushi, S.M., Al-Harthy, I.S., Almehrzi, R.S., Ambusiaidi, A.K., Al-Balushi, K.A., Al-Saad, K.K., Al-Aghbar, M., Al-Balush, M., (2022). Metacognitive Awareness Perceptions of Students with High and Low Scores On TIMSS-Like Science Tests. *International Journal of Cognitive Research in Science, Engineering and Education*.
- Ali Ramadan Elbaoui Shaddad, A.R.E. & Jember, B. (2024). A Step Toward Effective Language Learning: An Insight into The Impacts of Feedback-Supported Tasks and Peer-Work Activities on Learners' Engagement, Self-Esteem, And Language Growth. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education* volume 9 (39). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40862-024-00261-5>
- Almoslamani, Y. (2022), "The Impact of Learning Strategies on The Academic Achievement of University Students in Saudi Arabia", *Learning and Teaching in Higher Education: Gulf Perspectives*, Vol. 18 No. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LTHE-08-2020-0025>

- Alsalihi, H.D.A. (2020). Main Difficulties Faced by EFL Students in Language Learning. *Journal of College of Education for Women* 31(2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.36231/coedw.v31i2.1359>.
- Anastasia, A. (2022). A Literature Review of Language Learning Strategies.
- Arellano, D.C., (2018). Memory Learning Strategies in English as A Foreign Language in Vocational Studies.
- Arisman, R. (2020). The Relationship between Direct Language Learning Strategies and English Language Competence at Senior High School Students. *Journal of English for Academic*. [https://doi.org/10.25299/jshmic.2020.vol7\(2\).5339](https://doi.org/10.25299/jshmic.2020.vol7(2).5339).
- Armea, A.P., Castro, M., Llamado, M, Lotino, R., San Esteban, A., & Ocampo, D. (2022). English Proficiency and Literary Competence of English Major Students: Predictor for Effective Language and Literature Teaching. *Globus Journal of Progressive Education*.
- Bakhtiar, A. (2023). Investigating the Essay Writing Challenges Experience by Students at Bina Sarana Informatika University. *Research and Development Journal of Education*.
- Bal, A.P., Doganay, A., (2022). Problem-Solving and Student's Use of Metacognitive Skills. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*.
- Balini, I. & Jeyabalan, D., (2018). Role of Memory Strategy Training in Language Learning. *Bodhi International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Science*.
- Belkhir, S. (2020). *Cognition and Language Learning*. Camp Bridge Scholars Publishing.
- Bricki, N. & Green, J. (2007) *A Guide to Using Qualitative Research Methodology*. <https://fieldresearch.msf.org/handle/10144/84230>.
- Canisi, J. & Lambencio, G. (2023). Level Of Writing Competence and Conventional Errors of Students. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7530043>
- Cengelci, S. & Egmir, E. (2022). The Effect of 21st Century Learner Skills and Metacognitive Awareness on Early Teacher Identity. *International Journal of Education*.
- Chanderan, V., & Hashim, H. (2022). Language Learning Strategies Used by ESL Undergraduate Students. *Creative Education*, 13(3), 768-779.
- Chen, K. (2023). The Relationship between Learning Styles and Foreign Language Learning. *Journal of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences*. Vol. (8). <http://dx.doi.org/10.54097/ehss.v8i.4362>
- Chvalova, K. & Petrasova, B. (2020). Problems in Developing Language Competence in a Foreign Language. 13th annual International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation.
- Clark, V. & Ivankova, N. (2017). A Conceptual Framework for The Field of Mixed Methods Research. *Mixed Methods Research: A Guide to The Field* (pp. 1-2). SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781483398341>.
- Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (2016). *International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans*. <https://cioms.ch/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/WEB-CIOMS-EthicalGuidelines.pdf>
- Creswell, J. (2013). *Qualitative Research in Corporate Communication*. Blogs Baruch Site. <https://blogs.baruch.cuny.edu/>.
- Creswell, J. W. (2008). *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. Upper Saddle River, N. J. Pearson/Merill Education.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. Pearson Education, Incorporated.
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2011). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Los Angeles, Calif: SAGE Publications. https://toc.library.ethz.ch/objects/pdf/z01_978-1-4129-7517-9_01.pdf.
- Daar, D.F. (2020). *Problems of English Language Learning in Context*.
- De Castro, D. & Bactasa, G. M. (2023). Linguistic Competence of Senior High School Students in Ormoc City. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research and Innovation*. 1(3), 36-48. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8325526>.
- Degissew, D. & Beriso, I. (2022). Assessing Students' Use of Language Learning Strategies and Their Impact on Study Year. *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijll.20221002.13>
- DeKeyser, R. (2007) as cited by Smith, S. (2020). *Practice in a Second Language. What is Skill Acquisition Theory*. Perspectives from Applied Linguistics and Cognitive Psychology. New York: CUP.

- DeKeyser, R. (2007). *Skill Acquisition Theory. Theories in second language acquisition: An introduction*. American Psychological Association.
- Demir, S.B., & Pismek, N. (2018). A Convergent Parallel Mixed-Methods Study of Controversial Issues in Social Studies Classes: A class of ideologies. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practices*, 18(1), 119-149. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2018.1.0298>.
- Duran, J.A., Gutierrez, K.S., Ramirez, Y.A. (2022). Learning Strategies and their Influence on Foreign Language Skills: A Literature Review from the Oxford Taxonomy. *MEXTESOL Journal*
- El-Marsafy, & Abdu-Allah, (2021). The Effectiveness of Compensation Strategies for Developing Some Media Translation Skills for Educational Media Students at the Faculty of Specific Education.
- Eslit, E. (2023). English Language Competence Scale for English Major Students
- Evangelista, J., Mortega, R.J., Sugue, F.M., Pendon, C., Costales, R., & Ablen, A. (2019). Challenges Encountered in Learning Language Proficiency among Freshmen English Majors at B.C.P.
- Faqih, W.M., Susanto, D.A. & Nurani, M. W. B. (2023). The Implementation of Social Learning Strategy for Learning English Foreign Language in Vocational High School. *MARAS: Jurnal Penelitian Multidisplin*. Vol. (1).
- Faris, A. (2022). The Effect of English Proficiency on the Use of Communication Strategies. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360184986_The_effect_of_English_proficiency_on_the_use_of_communication_strategies
- Farrokh, P. (2019). On the Impact of Compensation Strategies on Language Learners' Vocabulary Development. *International Journal of Instruction* Vol.12, No.3. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2019.1237a>
- Fitroty, A.Z., (2022). Language Learning Strategies Used Among International Program Students: A Survey Study. English Language Department. Universitas Islam Indonesia.
- Galiza, C. (2022). Reading Competency and Academic Performance of Students. *Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers*, Vol. 13(1). 94–100. DOI: 10.47750/jett.2022.13.01.011.
- Gempes, G.P. (2023). Editable Templates for Mixed Methods Visual Concepts: Academia.edu. <https://rb.gy/bso8c>
- Ghambir, B.C. (2021). Challenges Faced by Bachelor Level Students While Speaking English. *Indonesian Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21093/ijeltal.v6i1.853>
- Gibbs, T. (2021). All About Language Comprehension: What It Is and How It Can Help Your Child Read. NWEA. Teach, Learn, Grow. The education blog
- Grenfella, M. & Harris, V. (2015). Memorization Strategies and the Adolescent Learner of Mandarin Chinese as a Foreign Language. *Linguistics and Education*.
- Groenewald, T. (2004). A Phenomenological Research Design Illustrated. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 3(1), 42-55. <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690400300104>.
- Habók, A., & Magyar, A. (2018). The Effect of Language Learning Strategies on Proficiency, Attitudes and School Achievement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 2358.
- Hagen, A.M.; Melvy-Lerbag, M.; Lervag, A. (2019). The Effect of Linguistic Comprehension Instruction on Generalized Language and Reading Comprehension Skills: A Systematic Review. Plain Language Summary on the Campbell Website. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cl2.1059>
- Haidar, S., Farrukh, F. & Dar, S.R. (2019). Desire for English in Youth: An Exploratory Study of Language Learners in Pakistan.
- Halcomb, E. J., & Hickman, L. (2015). *Mixed Methods Research*. <https://ro.uow.edu.au>.
- Hanson, W. E., Creswell, J. W., Clark, V. L. P., Petska, K. S., & Creswell, J. D.
- Hui, W. & Rashid, H. (2022). Analyze the Issues and Challenges in Teaching Writing Among English Teachers. *The International Journal of Applied Language Studies and Culture* 4(2):19-24. <http://dx.doi.org/10.34301/alsc.v4i2.34>
- Indeed Editorial Team (2022). Memorization Strategies. [Indeed.com](https://www.indeed.com).
- Islam, M.S., Stapa, M.B. Students' low proficiency in spoken English in private universities in Bangladesh: reasons and remedies. *Lang Test Asia* 11, 22 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-021-00139-0>
- Ismiatun, F., & Suhartoyo, E. (2022). An Investigation on The Use of Social Strategies in Online EFL Learning. *Education and Human Development Journal*, 7(01), 97–106. <https://doi.org/10.33086/ehdj.v7i01.2314>

- Izatullah, S., Nasir, R. & Gul, F. (2022). A Study to Examine the Relationship between English Language Proficiency and Academic Achievement of Students in Higher Education Institutions. *Global Educational Studies Review* 7(1). [http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2022\(VII-I\).17](http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2022(VII-I).17)
- Kadamovna, S.N. (2021). The Importance of Speaking Skills for Efl Learners. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology (LJIERT)* Vol. 8.
- Khaleq, A.E. (2018). Compensation Strategies for Overcoming EFL Young Learners' Oral Communication Difficulties. Faculty of Education, Fayoum University.
- Khanh Ly, C. (2024). Teachers' Roles on English Language Teaching for Promoting Learner-Centered Language Learning: A Theoretical Review. *International Journal of TESOL & Education* Vol. 4; No. 2. <https://doi.org/10.54855/ijte.24425>
- Koivula, M. (2022). Linguistic Compensation Strategies Finnish EFL learners Use in a Communicative Learning Situation.
- Kramprah, S.O. (2022). Impact Of Extensive Reading on English Language Competence: A Case Study of Jukwaa Senior High School. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology*, 2022 Vol. 7, Issue 1, ISSN No. 2455-2143, Pages 30-35.
- Krashen, S. (1970) as cited by Daw, E. (2023). What Is the Input Hypothesis. *Language Humanities Org.*
- Lem, N. C. (2019). Language Learning Strategies Among Vietnamese EFL High School Students. *Indonesian JELT: Indonesian Journal of English Language Teaching*, 14(1), 55-70.
- Lestari, M., & Wahyudin, A. Y. (2020). Language Learning Strategies of Undergraduate EFL Students. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 1(1), 25-30.
- Lopez, C. A. M., Moura, S.A., Delgado, S.C. (2020). Learning Listening Skills: A Means and An End in Foreign Language Acquisition. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1981-5794-e11863>.
- Lozano, J., Ilagan, A., & Maluluyon, L.J. (2020). Linguistic Competence and Academic Performance in English of Grade 11 Students in Sta. Teresa College. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education* 2020. V. (9). <http://dx.doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2020.5807>.
- Magriz, S.E., (2021). Learning Strategies: A Focus on the Use of Memory Strategies to Learn Archaic English.
- Mandasari, B., & Oktaviani, L. (2018). English Language Learning Strategies: An Exploratory Study of Management and Engineering Students. *Premise: Journal of English Education and Applied Linguistics*, 7, 61-78. <https://doi.org/10.24127/pj.v7i2.1581>
- Mantra, I.B.N, Handayani, N.D, Suwandi, I.N. (2019). Quantum Learning as A Natural Way to Improve Student's Language Competence. *International Journal of Applied Science and Sustainable Development (IJASSD)*.
- Marc. (2023). Linguistic Competence: What It Is and Why It Matters?
- Martinez, J.M. (2020). Understanding and Supporting Literacy Development Among English Learners: A Deep Dive into the Role of Language Comprehension *Sagepub.com/journals-permissions*. Vol. (6)(1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2332858420912198>.
- Mashrabovna, U. M., & Alievna, B. O. (2023). Cognitive Factors in Language Acquisition. *International Journal of Formal Education*.
- Mohammed, M. H. (2018). Challenges of Learning English as A Foreign Language (EFL) by Non-Native Learners. *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research*,3(4).
- Munhall, P. L. (2012). A Phenomenological Method. P. Munhall (Ed.), *Nursing Research: A Qualitative Perspective*, 113-176. <https://books.google.com.ph/>.
- Muslim U., Selatan, M.S., Nuraeni, N. (2021). Problems Encountered by Learners and How to Deal with Them in Learning English as A Foreign Language. (UHAMKA) *International Conference on ELT and CALL*.
- Nasution, A. K. P. (2022). Social Media Used in Language Learning: Benefits and Challenges. *Journal of Linguistics, Literature, and Language Teaching (JLLLT)*. Vol. 1. <https://doi.org/10.37249/jllt.v1i2.396>
- Nithidechaiwarachok, B., Maneekanon, O. & Bubphada, T. (2022). Exploring English Language Proficiency, English Language Problems, and English Needs Among First Year Undergraduate Students. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research* Vol. 21, No. 12, pp. 272-289. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.21.12.15>
- Ntereke, B. & Ramoroka, B. (2017). Reading Competency of First-year Undergraduate Students at University of Botswana: A Case study. *Communication and Academic Literacy*, University of Botswana, Botswan.
- Nurharjanto, A. & Widyantor, A. (2020). The Effect of Language Learning Strategy and Technology Toward Student's Writing Skills. *Jurnal Kependidikan* V. (2).
- Nyarko, K, Kugbey, N, Kofi, C.C, Cole, Y.A, Adentwi, K.I. (2018). English Reading Proficiency and Academic Performance Among

Lower Primary School Children in Ghana. Sage Journals. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244018797019>

Okmawati, M. (2020). The Role of Metacognitive Strategy in Learning English. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*.

Pachina, E. (2020). Common Problems for English Learners in the Philippines. *International TEFL and TESOL training*.

Pasumbu, H., & Macora, Y. (2020). Compensation As a Strategy in Teaching Reading to EFL Junior High School Students. *Sintuwu Maroso Journal of English Teaching*.

Petrosyan, Y. (2018). Assessing Research Protocols: Mixed Methods Research in Methods Workshop for the Ministry of Health and Long-Term Care.

Powell, S. (2023). Language Proficiency and the Relation to Word-Problem Performance in Emergent Bilingual Students with Mathematics Difficulties. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ldrp.12325>

Priya, K.L. & Priyadarshini, S.M. (2021). Effective Cognitive Strategies in English Language Learning. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*.

Rao, P.R. (2019). The Importance of Speaking Skills in English Classrooms. *Alford Council of Interantional English & Literature Journal (ACIELJ)*. Vol-2

Ratmanida, S.F. (2020). Student's Linguistics Problem in Reading Comprehension. Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Indonesia. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 539.

Renandya, W.A, Hidayati, M. & Ivone, F.M. (2023). *Teaching L2 Listening: Theory, Research and Practice*.

Rivas, R., Saiz, C., & Ossa, C. (2022). Metacognitive Strategies and Development of Critical Thinking in Higher Education. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.913219>

Rogde, K.; Hagen, Å.M.; Melby-Lervåg, M; Lervåg, A. (2019). The Effect of Linguistic Comprehension Instruction on Generalized Language and Reading Comprehension Skills: A Systematic Review. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 15(4). doi:10.1002/cl2.1059.

Rosyada, A. & Apoko, T.W. (2023). Investigating English Vocabulary Difficulties and Its Learning Strategies of Lower Secondary School Students. *JOLLT Journal of Languages and Language Teaching* Vol.11, No.3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33394/jollt.v%vi%i.8404>

Rubio, A.D. & Conesa, I.M. (2022). The Use of Digital Tools in The English Classroom in Spain. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 18(3).

Rusdin, N. M. (2018). Teachers' Readiness in Implementing 21st Century Learning. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8, 1293- 1306. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v8-i4/4270>.

Santos, A., Ilustre, R. & Fernandez, V. (2022). English Language Proficiency in the Philippines: An Overview. *International Journal of English Language Studies* 4(3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.32996/ijels.2022.4.3.7>

Sarwat, S., Ullah, N., Anjum, H.S., Bhuttah, T.M. (2021). Problems and Factors Affecting Students English Writing Skills at Elementary Level. *xIlkogretim Online - Elementary Education Online*. Vol 20 doi: 10.17051/ilkonline.2021.05.332.

Sasum, S., & Weeks, B. (2018). Why Some Thai Students Cannot Speak English Fluently? *RSU International Research Conference 2018*.

Scott, P. A. (2017). Ethical Principles in Healthcare Research. *Key Concepts and Issues in Nursing Ethics*, 191-205. <https://doras.dcu.ie/>

Septianasari, L., Huzunatul, F. & Baihaqi, Y. (2019). Mother Tongue Issues and Challenge in Learning English as Foreign Language. *International Journal of Indonesian Education and Teaching*. <https://doi.org/10.24071/ijiet.v3i2.1941>

Shahzad, M., Ahmad, N. & Akhtar, M. N. (2023). From Words to Research: Examining the Role of Language Competencies in Shaping Attitudes Towards Doing Research Projects. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.55737/qjssh.152288122>

Shakarami, A., Hajhashemi, K. & Caltabiano, N.J. (2017). Compensation Still Matters: Language Learning Strategies in Third Millennium ESL Learners. *Online Learning*, 21(3), 235-250: <http://dx.doi.org/10.24059/olj.v21i3.1055>.

Shakarami, A., Hajhashemi, K. & Caltabiano, N.J. (2017). Compensation Still Matters: Language Learning Strategies in Third Millennium ESL learners. *Online Learning*, 21(3), 235-250. <http://dx.doi.org/10.24059/olj.v21i3.1055>

Shankar, L.R. & Kumarl, R.N. (2021). The Importance of Listening Skill in Language Acquisition- The Problems Experienced & Strategies Adopted in Teaching Listening Skill. Ph.D Scholar, Arignar Anna Govt. Arts College, Villupuram. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology*.

- Shariyevna, K.J. & Atxamovna, D.I. (2020). The Importance of Listening in Foreign Language Learning. *EPR International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)* Volume: 6 |. Journal DOI: 10.36713/epra2013.
- Shawaqfeh, A.T., Jameel, J.A.S, Al-adwan, L.A.Y. & Khasawneh M.A.S. (2023). Interaction as a Mechanism to Enhance English Language Proficiency in the Classroom. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, Vol. 15(1) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1501.2>
- Siami, L.R., Chuaungo, D. (2021). A Study on the English Language Competency among Model English School Students in Aizawl City. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)* Volume 26, Issue 11, Series 2.
- Sison, N.R.M. (2022). Affective Strategies in Teaching and Learning English as a Second Language (ESL). *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 2(2), 79-90.
- Song, J. (2023). Korean Language Teachers' Vulnerability Over English Competency in Korean-Only Classrooms. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education* volume 8, Article number: 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40862-023-00185-6>
- Sosas, R.V. (2021). Technology in teaching speaking and its effects to students learning English. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 17(2), 958-970. Doi: 10.52462/jlls.66
- Strom, J. & Frojd, E. (2021). The Effects of Digital Tools on EFL/ESL Learners' Vocabulary Acquisition/Learning
- Sudarmo, S. (2021). The Importance of Speaking in English as A Foreign Language Between Skillful and Thoughtful Competencies: Studying Sociolinguistics Perspectives. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S1), 113-124. <https://doi.org/10.37028/lingcure.v5nS1.1321>
- Susanto, H. (2021). A Study on Students' Difficulties in Learning Vocabulary. *Journey: Journal of English Language and Pedagogy*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.33503/journey.v4i2.1413>
- Syukur, A. (2019). Encouraging Students to Have Positive Attitudes Toward Learning English. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30605/25409190.v3.02.122-130>
- Tabeti, S. (2019). The Relationship between Language Learning Strategy Use, Language Proficiency and Learner Gender: Case study of the first-year EFL students at the University of Mascara-ALGERIA. *East African Scholars Journal of Education, Humanities and Literature*. DOI: 10.36349/easjehl. 2019.v02i04.007
- Taleb, R.S. & Kurum, E.Y. (2022). The Effect of Foreign Language Strategies Students Use on Their Achievement in Learning English. *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJRSSH)* Vol. 9, Issue 2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6610781>
- Tedjaatmaja, H. & Robo, A.G.P., (2017). Affective Strategies Used by High Proficiency Learners at Hand Fortuna Center.
- Teng, F., & Zhang, L. J. (2021). Development of Children's Metacognitive Knowledge, And Reading and Writing Proficiency in English as A Foreign Language: Longitudinal Data Using Multilevel Models. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*.
- Teng, M.F., (2021). Exploring Awareness of Metacognitive Knowledge and Acquisition of Vocabulary Knowledge in Primary Grades: A Latent Growth Curve Modelling Approach Language Awareness.
- Triananda, N. (2022). Preference of English Language Education Students of Learning Styles. *Journal of Educational Study* Vol. 2 (1). DOI: 10.36663/joes. v2i1.271
- Vani, K.S & Naik, D.V. (2023). Significance of Listening Skills in Enhancing the Communication Skills. *SMART MOVES JOURNAL IJELLH*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.24113/ijellh.v11i7.11442>
- Vulchanova, M., (2023). Cognitive Skills Linked to Language Learning. *Improving Literacy & Communication Language Magazine*.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978 cited by Cherry, 2022). What Is Sociocultural Theory. Very well Mind is part of the Dotdash Meredith.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Wani, E. A. & Ismail, H. (2024). The Effects of Reading Habits on Academic Performance among Students in An ESL Classroom: A Literature Review Paper. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development* 13(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v13-i1/20207>
- Wirahyuni, K. & Martha, N. (2022). Cognitive Strategies on Language Learning. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Languages and Arts across Cultures (ICLAAC 2022)*. http://dx.doi.org/10.2991/978-2-494069-29-9_24.
- Wu, C.H., Koong Lin, H.C., Wang, T.H., Huang, T.H. & Huang, H.M. (2022). Affective Mobile Language Tutoring System for Supporting Language Learning. *Frontiers in Psychology Education*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.833327>.

Yadav, P. (2024). Exploring The Impact of English Language Proficiency on Cross-Cultural Communication Success. *An International Open Access, Peer-reviewed, Refereed Journal* Volume. 12 (3).

Yulia, A., Joshi, R.M., Husin, N.A. & Rahim, S. (2023). Enhancing English Proficiency through Social Circle and Vocabulary among Malaysian Adult Learners. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.24815/siele.v10i1.25740>

Zakaria, N. Hashim, H. & Yunus, M. (2019). A Review of Affective Strategy and Social Strategy in Developing Students' Speaking Skills. Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2019.1012232>.

Zarrinabadi, N., Lou, N.M. & Ahmadi A. (2022). Resilience In Language Classrooms: Exploring Individual Antecedents and Consequences. *An International Journal of Educational Technology and Applied Linguistics* Volume 109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2022.102892>

Zeng, X. (2018). A Study on the Improvement of English Writing Competence for College Students. Foreign Language School, Nanchang Normal University, Nanchang, Jiangxi, China. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, Vol. 9, No. 6, pp. 1344-1348. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0906.25>.

Zintz, S. (2018). Effectiveness of a Growth Mindset in Education. https://nwcommons.nwciowa.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1090&context=education_masters

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Cyril Glen B. Grapa

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Mary Ann Ronith P. Libago, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines